

INSTINCT

D1.1

INSTINCT use cases definition, requirements and system architecture

UPRC

Abstract

This deliverable contains the work conducted within Task 1.1 “Use cases definition, KPIs and system requirements specification” and Task 1.3 “System architecture and performance evaluation methodology”. The main objective of this deliverable is to specify the use cases and a set of system requirements that will address the core objectives of reconfigurability, immersiveness, self-healing and agility, interactive intelligence and energy efficiency, which will be the basis for all further work. In Section 1, the INSTINCT vision and objectives are presented, and in Section 2 the INSTINCT system concept is analyzed. Section 3 outlines use cases from initiatives that are relevant to the INSTINCT project. In Section 4 a detailed description of INSTINCT’s use cases and the associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are presented. Last, in Section 5, a description of the performance evaluation methodology that will be applied in the framework of INSTINCT is presented.

Keywords

6G, JCAS, system concept, use case, KPIs, requirements, evaluation strategy.

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Editors	Angeliki Alexiou (UPRC), Sotiris Droulias (UPRC)
Reviewers	all partners

Contributing partners

BARKHAUSEN INSTITUT GGMBH (BI)
UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS RESEARCH CENTER (UPRC)
ROBERT BOSCH GMBH (Bosch)
AALTO KORKEAKOULUSAATIO (AAL)
FRAUNHOFER HHI (FHG-HHI)
GREENERWAVE (GW)
NEC LABORATORIES EUROPE GMBH (NEC)
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE (Inria)
INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUEES DE LYON (INSAL)
FUNDACIO PRIVADA I2CAT, INTERNET I INNOVACIO DIGITAL (i2CAT)
OULUN YLIOPISTO (UOulu)
CENTRALESUPELEC (CS)
TELEFONICA INNOVACION DIGITAL (TID)

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Table of Contents

Executive summary	7
List of authors.....	8
List of figures and tables	9
Abbreviations.....	11
1 INSTINCT vision and objectives.....	12
1.1 Vision.....	12
1.2 Objectives.....	13
2 System concept	15
2.1 Pillars	16
2.2 Innovations beyond state-of-the-art	17
2.3 Usage scenarios.....	20
3 Overview of relevant 6G use cases and usage scenarios.....	23
3.1 ITU-R recommendation for the development of IMT-2030	23
3.2 ISAC standardization progress in 3GPP and ETSI	24
3.3 IEEE 802.11 use cases.....	26
3.4 Komsens-6G and Hexa-X	26
4 Analysis and taxonomy of INSTINCT use cases	29
4.1 Taxonomy of use cases	29
4.2 Sensing-aided connectivity	34
4.2.1 Topographic mapping	34
4.2.2 Dense urban coverage.....	36
4.3 Sensing-able connectivity	39
4.3.1 UAV-aided connectivity.....	39
4.3.2 RIS as a sensor.....	43
4.3.3 Smart kinetics	47
4.4 Multifunctional JCAS intelligence	51
4.4.1 Integration of sensing in wireless networks.....	51
4.5 Summary of critical KPI's	57
5 Initial considerations on system architecture and performance evaluation methodology ..	58
5.1 Overall methodology.....	58

5.2	Performance evaluation strategies	59
5.2.1	Analytical studies	59
5.2.2	Network performance evaluation.....	59
5.2.3	JCAS performance evaluation.....	60
5.2.4	Experimental testbeds and prototypes	60
5.3	System architecture considerations	63
6	Conclusions	65

Executive summary

The INSTINCT project aspires to deliver the theoretical framework and relevant waveforms, protocols and hardware design of an innovative "beyond communications" 6G architecture, which combines the benefits of sensing-assisted communications, communications-assisted sensing and the co-design of sensing and communications, leveraging intelligent surfaces and artificial intelligence/machine learning. The INSTINCT approach will be established, developed and evaluated, based on the following three pillars:

- PILLAR I - "Sense-to-communicate": Sensing-assisted communications aims to substantially improve radio spectrum usage by leveraging sensing information for supporting novel 'beyond communications' use cases.
- PILLAR II - "Communicate-to-sense": Communications-enabled sensing aims to transform the wireless network into a smart 'sense the world' platform, capable of providing JCAS-as-a-service functionalities and, thus, materializing the concepts of Electromagnetic Information Theory and wavefront engineering towards a wireless radio 'beyond transmitting bits', capable of sensing, detecting, mapping, and 'understanding' semantics.
- PILLAR III - Multi-functional JCAS Network Intelligence: Artificial Intelligence based optimization of wireless JCAS systems and algorithm design offers the 'brains' for the materialization of the co-design of sensing-assisted communications and communications-enabled sensing towards immersiveness, tunability, resilience and cyber-physical interaction.

Deliverable 1.1 sets the basis to build and achieve the main objectives of the INSTINCT project. This document is the first technical deliverable of the project and presents the results obtained in Tasks 1.1 and 1.3. This deliverable identifies the main use cases and the initial requirements that are taken into account for the INSTINCT project, representing a starting point for the work that will be carried out in the different work packages. Following the three pillars, the use cases in INSTINCT are organized in the following three categories:

- sensing-aided connectivity
- sensing-able connectivity
- multifunctional JCAS intelligence

This document also presents a list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that have been identified per use case, and are necessary to compare and evaluate the performance of the JCAS solutions that will be developed in the INSTINCT project. Finally, the deliverable addresses the performance evaluation methodology that will be applied in the framework of INSTINCT.

List of authors

Organization	Author	Contribution
BI	Padmanava Sen Hossein Dokhanchi	Sections 3.4, 4.3.1, 4.3.3
UPRC	Angeliki Alexiou Sotiris Droulias	Sections 1, 2, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 4.3.2, 5.2.1, 6, editing and final review
BOSCH	Alexander Artemenko	Section 4.3.3
AAL	Visa Koivunen	Sections 3.2, 4.4.1
FHG-HHI	Simon Schütze Robert Elschner	Sections 4.1, 4.2.1
GW	Youssef Nasser	Sections 4.2.2, 4.3.2
NEC	Francesco Devoti Vincenzo Sciancalepore	Sections 4.3.2, 5, editing and final review
INRIA/INSAL	Francois Baccelli Maxime Guillaud	Section 4.2.2
i2CAT	Andra Blaga Federico Campolo Carmen Delgado Filip Lemic Xavier Costa	Section 4.3.1
UOulu	Visa Tapio	Section 4.4.1
CS	Marco Di Renzo	Section 4.4.1
TID	Andra Lutu Paul Almasan	Section 4.4.1

List of figures and tables

List of figures

Figure 2.1: INSTINCT system concept for 6G networks.	15
Figure 2.2: Summary of INSTINCT pillars, objectives, innovations, demos and KPIs/KVIs.	20
Figure 3.1: Usage scenarios of IMT-2030.	24
Figure 4.1: Taxonomy of INSTINCT's use cases.....	30
Figure 4.2: RIS-aided topographic mapping in dynamic channel.....	35
Figure 4.3: RIS-aided topographic mapping in static channel.....	35
Figure 4.4: Left: the 3D model; the segments represent buildings seen from above - Right: the vision in a fixed direction where the heights and locations are depicted. The building blocking the view in this direction is denoted by a *. The RIS located on the top of this building is a natural candidate for NTN relaying.....	38
Figure 4.5: (a) Distance between the UAV positions and the center of the emergency area in a window time of 5 minutes (blue line). 3D positioning error in meters obtained for four tracked UEs in the same time window (red line). (b) Example of a UAV 3D prediction trajectory, obtained as output of the proposed algorithm for prediction [13].	42
Figure 4.6: RIS with power sensing capabilities collecting directional power measurements. ...	44
Figure 4.7: Example of privacy areas created with RIS to prevent eavesdrop of the signal [14].	45
Figure 4.8: Hierarchical RIS-assisted localization. Top row: Schematic illustration of the localization scheme, with the shaded regions marking the areas where the user location is successfully identified at each hierarchical level. Bottom row: simulated beams for each case.	46
Figure 4.9: Factory of the future vision of the company Robert Bosch GmbH [Source: Bosch].	49
Figure 4.10: Operational factory environment of the company Robert Bosch GmbH in Stuttgart with deployment of a mobile communication network [Source: Bosch].	51
Figure 4.11: Cellular JSAC-RIS system.....	53
Figure 4.12: SIM at the transmitter.	55
Figure 4.13: SIM as a network.	55
Figure 4.14: General overview of our proposed method with its potential inputs and outputs. ...	56
Figure 5.1: Left: Schematic of Cortex Lab infrastructure with multiple software defined radio nodes. Right: Related synchronization mechanisms.	61
Figure 5.2: Left: GW End-to-End 5G RIS testbed with dynamic RIS control. Right: FHG-HHI wideband testbed (direct RF synthesis) with integrated RIS.	62
Figure 5.3: Experimental evaluation of RIS real-world benefits.....	62

List of tables

Table 4.1: KPI's for JCAS-based, RIS-aided topographic channel mapping.	36
Table 4.2: KPI's for channel charting and the RIS-NTN use case.	39
Table 4.3: KPI's for rail track inspection and maintenance with JCAS-equipped UAVs.	40
Table 4.4: KPI's for base stations for control and surveillance of UAVs.	41
Table 4.5: KPI's for SAR localization framework in emergency environments.....	42
Table 4.6: KPI's for RIS in the ISAC network.....	45
Table 4.7: KPI's for user tracking and localization.....	47
Table 4.8: KPI's for collision avoidance and situational awareness in vehicles.	48
Table 4.9: KPI's for localization and data transmission for smart transportation in industrial manufacturing plants.	50
Table 4.10: KPI's for multicarrier JSAC/MIMO JSAC.	52
Table 4.11: KPI's for sensing in cellular networks.....	54
Table 4.12: KPI's for holographic surfaces for communication and sensing.	55
Table 4.13: KPI's for deep learning for realistic coverage map predictions.	57
Table 4.14: Summary of most critical KPI's for the three pillars of INSTINCT.....	57

Abbreviations

5G	Fifth Generation (mobile cellular networks)
6G	Six Generation (mobile cellular networks)
AESA	Active Electronically Scanned Array
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BER	Bit Error Rate
BS	Base Station
CSI	Channel State Information
DTS	Driverless Transport System
GHz	Gigahertz
HW	Hardware
JCAS	Joint Communications and Sensing
JCASaaS	JCAS-as-a-service
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LAA	Large Antenna Array
LIS	Large Intelligent Surface
LOS	Line of Sight
MBB	Mobile Broadband
MIMO	Multi-Input Multi-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications
mmWave	millimeter wave
MU	Multiuser
NTN	Non-Terrestrial Network
QoE	Quality of Experience
RF	Radio Frequency
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
SER	Symbol Error Rate
SIM	Stacked Intelligent Metasurface
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SW	Software
THz	Terahertz
UE	User Equipment
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication
XR	Extended Reality

1 INSTINCT vision and objectives

1.1 Vision

In recent years, research in industry and academia has revolved around identifying critical scenarios for 6G connectivity and inventing powerful and cost/power efficient enablers to address the corresponding challenges. There seems to be an agreement among the various stakeholders that critical usage scenarios will include a group of *extreme* evolution of the well-known 5G usage scenarios (MBB, URLLC, MMTc) and a group of *revolutionary* usage scenarios with a clear emphasis on 'beyond communications' objectives. Reinforcing intelligence by means of adopting AI/ML for optimising models, signals and protocols as an 'add-on' characteristic has received a lot of attention, as a potential promising direction towards this end, even though it may often result in non-scalable approaches and/or out of scale complexity increase.

The adoption of AI/ML could offer an evolutionary path to extreme communication scenarios, as a means to deal with the stochastic nature of a multiplicity of parameters and modelling deficits due to complexity in future networks. However, beyond communications intelligence in 6G could only be tackled by introducing inherent intelligence functionalities, technologies, and architectures, empowered by (i) situational awareness based on the capability to sense, measure, detect, monitor, map, 'read' the wireless environment (ii) the ability to control, tune, reconfigure, 'engineer' the wireless environment and (iii) the inherent intelligence to 'synthesize' on the fly wireless environment sensing capabilities with learning.

With the aspiration to lay the foundations of interactive, immersive, and intelligent 6G wireless networks, the vision of INSTINCT is to deliver breakthrough Joint Communications and Sensing (JCAS) technologies, to achieve "Beyond Communications" Quality of Experience (QoE) towards ubiquitous cyber-physical integration, global inclusion, reliable, resilient, and tactile connectivity 'beyond the transmission of bits'. INSTINCT aims to bring together advanced radar and sensing technologies, breakthrough intelligent material science and combined sensing and artificial (cyber-physical) intelligence into a unified framework and a coherent multifunction system concept. INSTINCT aims to contribute to the ongoing effort for convergence among radar and communications multiantenna technologies, multifunction hardware and RF designs, and waveform adaptivity. INSTINCT will investigate, theoretically analyse, design, develop, and showcase in proof-of-concept demonstrators, a ground-breaking multi-functional 6G system concept "*beyond communications*", in which spectrally and energy-efficient, immersive, interactive, reliable, and resilient connectivity in the bandwidth-rich mmWave and sub-THz regimes can be dynamically established and seamlessly reconfigured. By means of a novel notion of co-designing communications and sensing intelligence and leveraging breakthrough radar, intelligent surfaces and ML technologies for environment mapping and wavefront engineering, sensing becomes an integral functionality of network nodes, and the network becomes capable of 'sensing the world'. INSTINCT will enable the transition to a new wireless 'not just communications' era, where people, things, devices, and systems 'communicate to sense', 'sense to communicate' and are hyperconnected in a multi-functional integrated and interactive fashion.

1.2 Objectives

Interactive and Agile Sensing-aided Connectivity: Future connectivity is expected to be able to ‘sense’, map, monitor and interact offering real-time adaptation to variable environmental conditions. These capabilities will only be materialized by creating situational awareness about the radio environment and by facilitating agility, by means of the *ability to sense a large range of parameters* (including location, position, motion, shape etc.), real-time semantic processing of sensing data, as well as plug-and-play functionalities with automatic/autonomous configuration. AI, learning and decision-making capabilities will need to be native and ubiquitous in future systems, achieving different levels of automation, and customized optimization. Sensing-aided connectivity will -on the one hand- significantly enhance communication links performance by exploiting sensing towards more reliable link quality, resource allocation and interference management, and -on the other hand- enable several ‘beyond communications’ functions and services. For the latter, new performance targets need to be introduced, such as high accuracy, resolution in delay, angular and Doppler domains, low latency, fast convergence, energy, and resource efficient learning, etc. Interactive and agile sensing-aided communications will enable, for example, Mixed Reality applications and Digital Twinning capabilities.

Immersive and Resilient Sensing-able Connectivity: Reconfigurability, realised by means of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) and further enhanced with sensing capabilities, can evolve the ‘Beyond Shannon Communications’ system concept to ‘Beyond Communications’ concept by providing environment monitoring and dynamic adaptation in harsh (obstructed/NLOS) and volatile scenarios, efficient tracking of slowly moving users in dynamic blockage/obstruction conditions, detection of objects, shape identification etc. Acquired situational awareness and programmability of both the transceivers and the wireless propagation environment allows for wavefront engineering, which assigns ‘sensing’ attributes to RIS, thus enabling mapping, blockage avoidance and self-healing. The new multifunction hardware, algorithms and system design will need to optimize the energy efficiency of the operation. In addition, sustainability of the material resources and the avoidance of the e-waste need to be design targets. In that respect, the sustainability targets of the UN and the Green Deal by EU must have an impact on the selected KPIs of 6G.

Co-design of Communications and Sensing for Intelligent Connectivity: Communications and sensing will be co-designed for mutual benefit. This means sharing spectral, hardware and antenna resources, co-designing dual-function waveforms, developing theory, methods and signal processing algorithms for multifunction, multiuser and multi-target scenarios and optimizing the use of degrees of freedom such that desired performance level is achieved both in communications and sensing tasks. Optimization may be based on structured approaches or reinforcement learning. There are similar parallel RF convergence and multipurpose hardware development trends in circuit design and radar research communities, which can be taken into consideration. The integration of sensing and communications by means of co-design will enable a plethora of beyond-communications capabilities, such as imaging, mapping, and localization, human activity detection, which will introduce - in addition to reliable wireless connectivity - *novel connectivity features*, such as high resolution and accurate object detection and movement

and gesture characterization. Intelligent agents with perception, recognition and thinking capability will produce interactive behaviours, human-like interactions, also featuring emotional intelligence capabilities. Interactive intelligence will integrate a variety of information data such as voice, gestures, facial expressions and other physiological parameters, and the ability of responding / reacting in a tactile, natural manner.

2 System concept

Sustaining interactive, immersive, and intelligent connectivity "beyond just the transmission of large volumes of bits" ubiquitously available in 6G systems will require the exploitation of various frequency bands (both in the sub-6GHz and mmWave as well as sub-THz regime), the adoption of novel hardware technologies and intelligent materials, and the rethinking of Information Theory and Communication Theory framework and traditional design principles and architectures. Communications and sensing may be co-designed for mutual benefit and different tasks executed on a shared, multifunction HW. In this way, in the 6G era, the conventional system concept of a 5G evolution network as a universal resources (physical and virtual) manager will be radically transformed into the ground-breaking 'beyond communications' system concept of a fully reconfigurable and programmable, power-efficient, and resilient, intelligent connectivity provider by offering Sensing-as-a-Service as part of an integrated communications and sensing network architecture. The system concept of INSTINCT is presented in Figure 2.1.

Bringing to fruition this novel notion of co-designed communications and sensing in 6G networks entails the challenges of i) introducing novel propagation and channel modelling principles and a revolutionary communication theory approach, equipped with the appropriate waveforms, signalling, protocols and algorithms, for Joint Communications and Sensing, ii) devising a revolutionary approach to sensing -beyond the conventional sensor/actuator and radar concepts- where MIMO, holographic radios, intelligent surfaces and so far unexplored capabilities for wavefront tunability are used to materialize 'beyond communications' functionalities and iii) delivering a flexible and powerful synthesis of sensing technologies, joint communications and sensing and AI/ML capabilities into a holistic wireless network optimisation framework.

Figure 2.1: INSTINCT system concept for 6G networks.

2.1 Pillars

To develop such a system, cutting-edge technology components are to be designed, including antenna arrays, metasurface-based holographic radios, RF-frontends, waveforms, baseband processing, medium access control protocols, sensing technologies and ML-based resources and network management tools and synthesized into a novel 'beyond communications' architecture and, most importantly, a suitable performance evaluation framework (with the most relevant KPIs/ KQIs) needs to be specified. The highest priority for INSTINCT will be to identify, assess and address the critical technology gaps and invent, optimise, and demonstrate the appropriate enablers, expected to catalyse the road to 6G. In particular, the INSTINCT approach will be established, developed and evaluated based on the following three pillars:

PILLAR I – “Sense-to-communicate”: Reconfigurable, immersive, self-healing, interactive and energy-efficient mmWave and sub-THz wireless connectivity will be achieved by means of advanced, power-efficient integration of radar technologies into the multifunction transceiver design and network architecture. The two most critical success factors for the incorporation of sensing are: the modelling and learning situational awareness about radio environments, design, optimization and adaptation of the suitable waveforms and the efficient resources allocation and interference management by exploiting the acquired awareness. The objective of sensing-assisted communications is to substantially improve radio spectrum usage by leveraging sensing information for supporting novel 'beyond communications' use cases. The integration of sensing opens a new dimension and numerous degrees of freedom in modelling and virtually mapping the wireless environment, assisting wireless access technologies with contextual information, optimizing, adapting and learning transceiver operational parameters and transforming the wireless systems towards deterministic networking principles materialization.

PILLAR II – “Communicate-to-sense”: Communications beyond the Shannon paradigm together with increasing the sensing, localization and mapping accuracy beyond the conventional Cramér-Rao lower bound, by means of reconfigurable intelligent materials/surfaces, large intelligent surfaces (LIS) and massive MIMO architectures, aim to support joint communications and sensing functionalities both at the physical layer and network level, and guarantee connectivity reliability, agility and reconfigurability. This approach of communications-enabled sensing is expected to transform the wireless network into a smart 'sense the world' platform, capable of providing JCAS-as-a-service (JCASaaS) functionalities and, thus, materializing the concepts of Electromagnetic Information Theory and wavefront engineering towards a wireless radio 'beyond transmitting bits', capable of sensing, detecting, mapping, and 'understanding' semantics. Co-design of sensing and communications and cooperation among wirelessly connected users is vital for achieving the above objectives.

PILLAR III – Multi-functional JCAS Network Intelligence: Artificial Intelligence based optimization of wireless JCAS systems and algorithm design, leveraging the reconfigurability and programmability of intelligent materials, by means of model-based optimization, together with data-driven machine learning approaches, can optimise the architecture, resources allocation, propagation modelling and waveform design. Intelligence, based on situational awareness, real-time learning and adaptation, offers the ‘brains’ for the materialization of the *co-design of sensing-assisted communications and communications-enabled sensing* towards immersiveness, tunability, resilience and cyber-physical interaction.

2.2 Innovations beyond state-of-the-art

State-of-the-art

Radio frequency (RF) sensing is usually passive, as in localization, passive radars (that may use communications signals as signals of opportunity) or active, where sensors probe their operational environment by emitting self-generated energy and observe the signals reflected off the targets as in radars or radio frequency imaging. Currently, the sensing tasks in wireless communications systems involve conventional channel estimation and direction of arrival estimation that are then directly used to estimate transmitted payload data sequence or form beams towards wireless users to enhance the signal to noise ratio. Nevertheless, there is a multitude of RF sensing tasks with different optimality criteria starting from target detection, parameter estimation, tracking, target recognition, imaging, and clutter mitigation. RF sensing systems and wireless communication systems can coexist within the same spectrum, but there is no information exchange between them to mitigate interference, optimize performance, or adjust operational parameters. As a result, RF sensing and wireless communications are currently usually performed in separate systems in distinct platforms and in non-cooperative or competitive settings. They have different objectives and performance criteria, for example, data rate or quality of service in communications and detection probability or the Cramer-Rao Bound of target parameter estimation. Different radio systems co-exist and consider other radio systems as non-cooperative systems, causing unintentional interference that needs to be mitigated to achieve desired performance levels. Therefore, there is a compelling need for performing communications and sensing jointly, so that signals considered to be interferences in non-cooperative setting can be exploited for sensing or communications purposes, with efficient spectrum usage and hardware/circuit cost reduction.

Currently, there is a tremendous opportunity to improve the performances of co-existing sensing and communications, by taking advantage of the technology convergences and cooperating or even co-designing the sensing and communications tasks, HW and antenna systems. Note that there is ongoing convergence among the modern wireless communications and different radio frequency sensing systems, such as radars [1]. Modern multiantenna technologies and large aperture antenna arrays are used in radar and communications as in AESA (active electronically scanned array) radars and massive MIMO base-stations to perform high resolution spatial processing. Similarly, both transmitters and receivers are fully adaptive and capable of waveform

diversity, optimization and adaptation. There is also a parallel convergence trend in radar systems where fully adaptive multifunction radars are being developed. In RF circuit design there is convergence towards multifunction operation and sharing the HW resources within circuits.

Importantly, RISs have the major feature of customizing complex wireless environments as one desires, without requiring additional energy sources. In spite of the extensive literature and the many European-funded projects, these new network nodes have merely been considered as nearly passive reflecting surfaces for enhancing the coverage in blind spot areas. RISs are, however, made of reconfigurable elements, with properties that go much beyond smart reflectors [2] and are, therefore, ideal for programming and dynamically reconfiguring the wireless environment.

Beyond state-of-the-art

A key component of designing **sensing-aided communications** is to build and maintain awareness on the dynamic radio environment. Knowledge of the locations of mobile users can simplify mmWave beam alignment complexity and allow managing interferences in the spatial domain. In INSTINCT, sensing will be used to build and learn situational awareness to enhance and optimize communications performance. To this end, joint objective functions, rewards and regret models for optimization and learning will be developed in INSTINCT. The design of waveforms suitable for cooperative sensing and communications systems will be targeted, along with information exchange with communications users to create and share awareness about radio environments and interferences. For example, by utilizing radio environment sensing and awareness of time-frequency-space varying spectrum, transceiver operational parameters can be optimized, or learned, and consequently communication performance can be improved.

To design **sensing-able communications**, INSTINCT will create realistic models for cell-free network architectures complemented with (HR-)RISs to support enhanced network operation, performance, and efficiency. In addition to the communications functionalities, the network will be used as a sensor to provide different sensing services: positioning of the active users, localization of passive dynamic objectives, which are not connected to the network, and learning the static environment on the times when the network data traffic load is low or moderate. Realistic channel and blockage models will be incorporated to the design and optimisation. Note that, current communication models for RISs are oversimplified, are not physically consistent, and are often not used correctly. The unique features of RIS and LIS (spherical wavefront, mutual coupling, large bandwidth, strict power/complexity) need brand-new physical models, new optimization problems to tackle, and new joint waveforms [3]. In INSTINCT, we will introduce a unified approach for modelling surfaces that can be used for reconfigurable and dynamic holographic transceivers to be integrated into wireless network design frameworks.

Connectivity in 6G networks goes beyond just reliable transmission of large volumes of data; 6G networks cannot be treated as communication-centric since for the first time they provide multi-functional connectivity, including communications, sensing, monitoring, and imaging. In the framework of **Multi-functional JCAS Network Intelligence**, INSTINCT will investigate the development of multi-function RIS that enables communication, sensing, and energy harvesting on the same platform [4]. Such platforms not only enable the reconfigurability of the wireless environment through smart reflections, but they also make the RIS as a platform that senses the

electromagnetic field, inferring the status of the network and using it for network optimization, ensuring energy autonomy as well. For the integration of sensing, intelligent surfaces, and their design optimization, INSTINCT will use signal processing and information theory, and will leverage optimization theory, machine learning and stochastic geometry, fields that play an important role in interference management, beam-squint problem of the wideband JCAS, hot-spot analysis of communications and sensing, and improvement of coverage obtained by adaptive reconfiguration of the connections in the presence of moving obstacles and eventually of RISs. Advanced radio communication technologies, such as massive MIMO, network MIMO, and multi-functional RIS, will play a significant role in INSTINCT as multi-functional enablers for both sensing and communications. Ultimately, INSTINCT aims to optimize and manage the resource utilization along with seamless integration of reconfigurable technologies to achieve tunability and programmability beyond state of the arts in the new 6G era of agility and autonomous operation.

INSTINCT will carry out a substantial number of well-planned and coordinated research and development tasks, all directed towards realizing the three visionary pillars and achieving the corresponding objectives. The tasks involve engaging in analytical and fundamental studies, algorithm and signal processing, wavefront engineering and sensing-based situational awareness, resource management and network modules design, as well as network architecture and sensing-based, model-based and data-driven optimization. For each of the three objectives, the key technology breakthroughs (fundamental, analytical, waveforms, algorithmic, HW/implementation) will be demonstrated, validated and evaluated by means of

- Definition of a proof-of-concept software (SW) simulation and hardware (HW) demonstration platform,
- Implementation of the INSTINCT demonstration platform, and
- Evaluation of the INSTINCT system performance.

This work is performed in order to

- Experimentally validate on SW and HW the theoretical findings and technological developments,
- Qualitatively and quantitatively assess the practical limitations and obstacles of 'Sense-to-Communicate', 'Communicate-to-sense' and Multi-functional JCAS Network Intelligence in a real-life operating environment,
- Assess the feasibility of the proposed architecture and individual components/functionalities integration, and
- Identify possible accelerators for the adoption of the 3 envisioned pillars in the roadmap of 6G, limitations that may consist of showstoppers and ways to overcome the associated obstacles.

Figure 2.2 summarizes the overall vision of INSTINCT, the pillars, objectives, innovations, as well as the associated demos and measurable criteria of success.

Figure 2.2: Summary of INSTINCT pillars, objectives, innovations, demos and KPIs/KVIs.

2.3 Usage scenarios

The co-design of sensing and communications supported by intelligent surfaces and AI/ML will become core enabler for ultra-fast, agile, reconfigurable and resilient 6G networks and will catalyse the digital and green transformation of future smart networks and services. Efficient support of upcoming innovative applications with performance requirements, beyond current technological capabilities, such as the Internet of Senses, holographic communications, massive digital twinning, extended reality (XR), full autonomous driving, flying networks, digital participation, can only become a reality if: (i) relevant, appropriate and targeted usage scenarios are adequately specified, (ii) suitable KPIs/KVIs are accurately and unambiguously defined and (iii) powerful technological breakthroughs are designed in the context of energy/cost-efficient service infrastructures, seamlessly integrating sensing, connectivity and computational functionalities. By combining the interactive intelligence of sensing with the immersive intelligence of holographic surfaces and the artificial intelligence of ML, INSTINCT aspires to contribute to the definition of new/relevant KPIs/KVIs, the formulation of a revolutionary theoretical framework, and the invention/design of ground-breaking technological cornerstones of 6G ‘beyond communications’ systems. INSTINCT innovations will help engineer a major paradigm shift and a transition from the communication-centric networks era to the new multi-functional networks era, embracing and materializing inclusion, sustainability, resilience and hyperconnected intelligence. To execute this ambitious plan, INSTINCT will first specify the attributes and parameters of three carefully selected representative usage scenarios.

Usage Scenario 1:

I3 (Interactive, Immersive and Intelligent) mobility (Localization, tracking and traffic management for automotive/drones)

Drones, vehicles and other autonomous agents in future networks are seen as a way to extend the notion of coverage to that of intelligent connectivity. They can be essential in emergency cases when backhaul/fronthaul nodes stop operating due to malfunctioning or physical disaster. Due to the failure of a remote radio head, a drone can be deployed with attached remote radio head to serve the affected users. Vehicles can be equipped with transceivers for reliable fast communication of road/traffic conditions to preceding cars (vehicle-to-vehicle - V2V). Moreover, traffic lights may dispatch critical information to vehicles approaching (vehicle-to-everything -V2X). Intelligent connectivity in dynamic network topologies will largely depend on the integration of advance sensing technologies (based on either radar or intelligent surfaces sensing functionalities) and Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning principles. Integrated sensing and communication are natural in scenarios with autonomous agents, as they rely on a variety of sensors (e.g., radar, camera, lidar) to map their environment and localize themselves, while communication is needed for coordination and sharing information beyond the field of view of local sensors. To adequately support such a dynamic network topology, fast varying wireless propagation and various associated challenges, such as around-the-corner connectivity, blind spots etc., the use of intelligent surfaces and holographic MIMO is key. I3 mobility scenario combines requirements of autonomous mobility, accurate localization and tracking/navigation with reliability, availability, resilience and intelligence.

Usage Scenario 2:

I3 environment monitoring (localization/positioning/imaging/radio environment mapping/surveillance)

The requirements for dynamic reconfiguration in obstructed/NLOS scenarios and tracking slowly moving users introduce several challenges with respect to transceivers adaptation, channel estimation, localization, shape identification and resource management. Immersive connectivity beyond simple transmission of bits will enable Augmented/Virtual/Mixed Reality applications empowered by holographic communication technologies and Digital Twinning capabilities in industrial, office, home and other environments. I3 environment monitoring entails: i) dynamic environment mapping (with respect to propagation, radio conditions, shape, movement, semantics etc., ii) security surveillance, including incident and proximity detection, iii) remote monitoring of industrial processes or office/home/health applications. In all three cases,

accurate localization, sensing, extremely low latency and agile reconfiguration allow for super-fast, ubiquitous in space and time and omni-present 'immersive' user experience.

Usage Scenario 3:

I3 Internet of Senses (augmented human sensing, well-being monitoring, user interfaces, gaming)

The integration of sensing functionalities is expected to play a decisive role in realizing the vision of digitization and programmability of the physical world, the real time interaction between virtual and physical entities and the co-design of communication and sensing systems. The latter would require the seamless incorporation of multiple heterogeneous sensing capabilities and the efficient design of multidimensional sensing approaches, including gesture recognition, augmented human sensing, cyber-physical interaction etc. Ultra-high precision, resolution, synchronization and analysis of heterogeneous data signals is of paramount importance as part of the extended reality (XR) evolution.

The Internet-of-Things can be brought to the next level by introducing the Internet-of-Senses paradigm: a multitude of sensing devices/functionalities that can be plugged into the existing network infrastructure without requiring complex installation procedures and perform RF sensing beyond radar (e.g., spectroscopy). Radio frequency communications and radar signals may be used in a variety of emerging sensing applications, including crowd and human activity sensing, well-being monitoring, sports analytics, user interfaces and RF fingerprinting. RF sensing modality is also convenient from the privacy point of view unlike cameras. Co-design and cooperation among different radios may provide radically new capabilities in a variety of applications. Moreover, the emerging holographic MIMO and RIS technologies, which open up a vast number of opportunities and support (co-designed) sensing and communications, offer programmable and reconfigurable connectivity beyond the transmission of bits. AI/ML and semantic communications principles are cornerstones in establishing intelligence on the Internet of Senses.

Motivated by these challenging scenarios, INSTINCT proposes to identify, investigate and develop suitable key technologies, system concepts and network architectures, namely

- Sensing-assisted communications innovations leveraging situational awareness in order to 'communicate to sense',
- Communications-assisted sensing innovations leveraging RIS and cell free MIMO inherent capabilities in order to 'sense to communicate, and
- Novel approaches to the co-design of communication and sensing with respect to spectrum, waveform and HW.

INSTINCT aims to *transform* the JCAS opportunity into a powerful 6G enabler leveraging the *synthesis* of the above 3 pillars into an intelligent beyond communications network capable of 'sensing - tuning - interacting with the world'.

3 Overview of relevant 6G use cases and usage scenarios

Recently, the definition and specification of use cases and usage scenarios of 6G has been under investigation, with the objective to quantify the 6G system requirements and performance targets. The vision of INSTINCT for breakthrough JCAS will be put into test with use cases that are aligned with the general vision of 6G. A detailed description of the INSTINCT use cases will be given in the next section. In this section we overview use cases and usage scenarios from various initiatives, such as standardization groups and projects, which are closely related to the use cases of INSTINCT.

3.1 ITU-R recommendation for the development of IMT-2030

With the evolution of information and communications technologies, IMT-2030 is expected to support enriched and potential immersive experience, enhanced ubiquitous coverage, and enable new forms of collaboration [5]. The advances in human-machine interfaces, interactive and high-resolution video systems such as extended reality (XR) displays, haptic sensors and actuators, and/or multi-sensory (auditory, visual, haptic or gesture) interfaces, give promise that IMT-2030 will offer humans immersive experiences that are virtually generated or happening remotely. In the physical world, humans and machines are expected to continuously interact with each other, working with a digital world that extends the real world by using a large number of advanced sensors and AI. Sensing information, while preserving security, is envisaged to be communicated in certain environments and across networks in a distributed manner to facilitate specialized services. Sensing the physical surroundings together with appropriate AI could further enhance situational awareness and support various innovative applications, such as high precision positioning and localization of devices and objects, high resolution and real-time 3D-mapping for automated and safe driving/transport, digital twins and industrial automation. Other opportunities include human activity (e.g., gesture) recognition, personal health sensing, sports analytics, environment monitoring and material inspection.

IMT-2030 is expected to integrate sensing and AI-related capabilities into communication and serve as a fundamental infrastructure to enable new user and application trends. The integration of sensing and communication is expected to become a key enabler for a wide range of use cases. In Recommendation [5], usage scenarios of IMT-2030 include Immersive Communication, Hyper Reliable and Low-Latency Communication, Massive Communication, Ubiquitous Connectivity, Artificial Intelligence and Communication, and Integrated Sensing and Communication (see Figure 3.1). The Integrated Sensing and Communication usage scenario facilitates new applications and services that require sensing capabilities. It makes use of IMT-2030 to offer wide area multi-dimensional sensing that provides spatial information about unconnected objects as well as connected devices and their movements and surroundings. Typical use cases include IMT-2030 assisted navigation, activity detection and movement tracking (e.g., posture/gesture

recognition, fall detection, vehicle/pedestrian detection), environmental monitoring (e.g., rain/pollution detection), and provision of sensing data/information on surroundings for AI, XR and digital twin applications. Along with the provided communication capabilities, this usage scenario requires support of high-precision positioning and sensing-related capabilities, including range/velocity/angle estimation, object and presence detection, localization, imaging and mapping.

Figure 3.1: Usage scenarios of IMT-2030.

3.2 ISAC standardization progress in 3GPP and ETSI

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has listed use cases for ISAC systems in [6]. Many of the 3GPP use cases include animal or human detection and vehicle tracking in various environments. In addition to target presence detection, ISAC is proposed for health monitoring and gesture recognition. Use cases for environment sensing such as rainfall monitoring and flooding detection are also included. In [7], 3GPP describes the sensing technology as part of the 5G system for enabling new services and use cases. 5G wireless sensing service provides new possibilities for enhanced usage of the telecommunication infrastructure. It provides input to different verticals (e.g., UAVs, smart home, V2X, factories, railways, public safety, etc.) enabling applications offering e.g., intruder detection, assisted automotive maneuvering and navigation, trajectory tracing, collision avoidance, traffic management, health and activity monitoring. In some cases, 5G wireless sensing can also use non-3GPP type sensors (e.g., Radar, camera) to further support the 3GPP-based sensing.

The operation of the 5G wireless sensing service, a.k.a. sensing operation, relies on processing the transmissions, reflections, and scattering of wireless sensing signals. 5G wireless sensing,

therefore, has the opportunity to enhance the 5G system from a communication network to a wireless communication and sensing network, where it uses 5G entities to sense objects and the environment in its surroundings. Sensing operation can be implemented in different ways, from radar like sensing where the sensing transmitter and sensing receiver are co-located in the same entity (monostatic sensing), to have the sensing receiver and sensing transmitter in different entities (bistatic sensing). A more advanced scenario with multiple sensing transmitters and receivers is also possible (multistatic sensing). The reflections of the sensing signal sent from the sensing transmitter are received by the sensing receiver and processed to obtain characteristics of the sensed object and its environment (e.g., location). Non-3GPP based sensing is when information from non-3GPP sensors is used to determine characteristics of objects and their environment. These non-3GPP sensors could include radar camera or Wi-Fi sensing. Non-3GPP sensing data from these non-3GPP sensors, if available, can be used in 5G wireless sensing to achieve improved sensing result, or in any other way to enhance the sensing service.

Sensing operations, such as authorization, and parameters such as sensing area, sensing operation period and sensing operation time window etc., could be configured and adjusted for efficient use of all kinds of resources, such as energy and radio spectrum, etc. 5G wireless sensing service also brings challenges related to confidentiality and privacy. There is a need to protect the sensing data from unauthorized access, interception and eavesdropping, but also to make sure the 5G wireless sensing service is in compliance with regulatory requirements. The introduction of sensing capabilities can enable tracking of people and objects in the environment, including people not carrying UEs.

ETSI ISG ISAC is in the process of defining use cases that are not covered in [6]. These include use cases for human motion recognition, collaborative robots based on digital twins, and airborne-based-sensing for environmental reconstruction. Other use cases under discussions include real-time monitoring of health and disaster risk, remotely controlled robots for senior citizen monitoring and care, environmental sensing for enhanced healthcare monitoring, body proximity sensor, emergency search and rescue, micro-deformation sensing, precise localization for robot grasping. The use case list for the ISG ISAC has not yet been finalized.

ETSI ISG RIS has formulated six use cases for utilizing RIS-units in ISAC systems [8]. These use cases are divided into two groups, active and passive sensing and three cases are identified for both groups. In active cases, a RIS is used to forward a sensing signal transmitted by a base station (BS) to a target area. In Active Case-A1, a separate node (i.e., another node than a UE or BS) is deployed for the sensing, while in Active-Case-A2 the RIS forwards both the sensing signal to a target area and a response signal back to a BS. In Active Case-B, a RIS unit is equipped with a sensing receiver. It forwards the sensing signal from a BS to the transmit area and receives and potentially process the sensing signal before forwarding the result of the sensing to the network. In passive sensing Case-A, a RIS is acting as a sensing receiver listening transmissions from the target area (RIS is operating as a receiving antenna). In passive sensing Case-B1, a RIS unit forwards transmissions from the target area to a BS, the RIS does not have any receiving capability. In passive sensing case-B2, a RIS forwards transmissions from a target area to a UE, and the UE acts as a sensing node.

3.3 IEEE 802.11 use cases

The IEEE 802.11 working group for WLAN Standards specifies Wi-Fi use cases for room sensing, gesture recognition, health care, 3D vision, and in-car sensing [9].

Room sensing: presence detection, counting the number of people in the room, localization of active people (smart meeting room), motion detection in a room, home security (detection of presence of intruders in a home), tracking persons in a room and pointing the sound of an audio system at those people (audio with user tracking), counting number of people in a store, their location, speed of movement (store sensing), and home appliance control (tracking person and motion/ gesture detection).

Gesture recognition: movements from short range (finger movement), to medium range (hand movement), and large range (full body movement). It includes aliveness detection (determination whether a close by object is alive or not), face/body recognition (selection of the identity of a person from a set of known persons), proximity detection (detection of object in close proximity of device), and home appliance control (gesture detection).

Health care: fall detection/abnormal position detection, remote diagnostics (measurements of breathing rate, heart rate etc.), surveillance/monitoring of elder people and/or children (tracking person and presence detection), and sneeze sensing (detecting and localizing the target human and sneeze droplet volume).

3D vision: building a 3D picture of an environment, using multiple STA.

In-car sensing: detection of humans in car, detection of driver sleepiness, and detection aid.

3.4 Komsens-6G and Hexa-X

The following use cases are reported in the deliverable of a BMBF supported project Komsens-6G [10]. These use cases are also reported in Hexa-X (EU flagship project) publication [11].

Sensing-Aided Communication

Beam-Specific Power Control for Electromagnetic Field (EMF) Exposure Management: In 6G networks, real-time sensing information is integrated with communication systems to optimize performance and efficiency. One crucial application is the management of EMF exposure. Sensing-aided communication allows base stations to dynamically adjust the power of their antenna beams based on real-time environmental and user data. This targeted beamforming ensures that power is concentrated only where needed, reducing unnecessary EMF exposure and enhancing the overall safety and efficiency of the network. By continuously monitoring the location and movement of users, as well as environmental factors such as obstacles and weather conditions, the system can adapt the beam patterns to maintain optimal signal strength while minimizing exposure. This real-time adjustment is particularly important in urban areas where high-density deployment of base stations can lead to higher cumulative EMF exposure.

Public Safety

Monitoring and Tracking UAVs: Sensing technology in 6G enables advanced monitoring and tracking of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). This capability is crucial for ensuring airspace security, especially in sensitive areas such as airports, government buildings, and public events. Sensors can detect the presence of UAVs, identify their type and trajectory, and even communicate with them to prevent unauthorized access. This enhances security and helps prevent potential threats posed by rogue or malfunctioning drones.

Detecting Suspicious Activities in Highway Parking Lots: Highway parking lots are prone to various suspicious activities, including theft, vandalism, and unauthorized access. Sensing systems can monitor these areas in real-time, using video surveillance, motion detectors, and other sensors to detect unusual behaviour. When suspicious activities are identified, alerts can be sent to law enforcement or security personnel, enabling a quick response to prevent incidents and ensure public safety.

Monitoring Patterns at Railroad Crossings: Railroad crossings are critical points where accidents can occur due to human error, mechanical failure, or adverse weather conditions. Sensing technology monitors the movement of vehicles and pedestrians near crossings, as well as the status of crossing gates and signals. This data helps in predicting potential collisions and issuing timely warnings to prevent accidents. In addition, sensing systems can detect anomalies in crossing operations and alert maintenance crews to address issues promptly.

Detecting Road Traffic Congestion at Intersections: Sensing systems at intersections can detect real-time traffic conditions, including congestion, accidents, and flow patterns. This information is used to optimize traffic signal timings, reroute traffic, and provide drivers with real-time updates. Improved traffic management reduces delays, enhances safety, and lowers emissions by minimizing idling times.

Environmental Sensing for Disaster Response: Environmental sensors play a vital role in detecting and responding to natural disasters such as rainfall and flooding. These sensors monitor weather conditions, water levels, and soil moisture to provide early warnings of potential floods. The data collected helps disaster response teams to prepare and respond more effectively, minimizing damage and saving lives. Real-time environmental sensing also aids in coordinating rescue and relief operations by providing accurate situational awareness.

Smart Logistics and Smart Factories

Navigation of Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs): In smart logistics and factory environments, AGVs rely on sensing technologies for navigation and operation. These vehicles use a combination of cameras, LIDAR, and other sensors to map their surroundings, avoid obstacles, and optimize their routes. Sensing-aided navigation enhances the efficiency and safety of AGVs, allowing them to transport goods and materials seamlessly within warehouses and production facilities. This leads to improved operational efficiency, reduced costs, and minimized downtime due to accidents or misnavigation.

Smart City Initiatives

Detecting Wrong-Way Drivers: In urban areas, wrong-way driving poses a significant risk to traffic safety. Sensing technologies such as cameras and radar systems are deployed to detect vehicles traveling in the wrong direction. When a wrong-way driver is detected, the system can trigger alerts on digital signage, inform other drivers via navigation apps, and notify law enforcement to intercept the vehicle. This proactive approach enhances road safety by preventing potential collisions and reducing the risk of accidents caused by wrong-way driving.

These use cases highlight the transformative potential of integrating advanced sensing technologies within the 6G framework. By leveraging real-time data and intelligent systems, 6G aims to enhance communication services, public safety, disaster response, and operational efficiency across various sectors, contributing to a safer, more efficient, and connected world.

4 Analysis and taxonomy of INSTINCT use cases

With every project partner taking their individual approach to formulating use cases, including vocabulary, design language, and technological viewpoint, and projecting their place in the future communications ecosystem, grouping the use cases in a logical manner and unifying them in terms of requirements and success metrics is paramount. This section aims to introduce a taxonomy and detailed description of INSTINCT's use cases, according to the thematic pillars first laid out in the project proposal.

4.1 Taxonomy of use cases

INSTINCT aims to accelerate the convergence of communication and sensing functionality in future networks, identifying and exploiting synergies in their design. It is important to point out that the spectrum of use cases considered in this project represents a non-exhaustive subset of the entire catalogue of possible applications. We forego exploring the full breadth of possible applications in favor of focusing on more concrete details of some specific use cases, chiefly among them the system requirements arising from the unique challenge of fusing functionalities traditionally thought of as diametrically opposed. Nonetheless, the list of explored use cases covers a range of applications, from the industrial to the consumer market, and from the backhaul to the fronthaul side of future networks.

The objectives defined therein distinguish between concepts for connectivity that are **sensing-aided**, **sensing-able**, and **multi-functional and/or intelligent** in nature. While neither the communication nor the sensing aspect takes definitive precedence over the other due to the very concept of JCAS, this classification emphasizes the nature of the relationship between the two functions. Whereas the first two categories utilize one function in service of the other, the latter focuses on the flexibility afforded by a connectivity system designed from the ground up with shared communication and sensing duties in mind – a comprehensive rethinking of the very nature of information networks. Another dimension for the location of relevant use cases in the multi-dimensional space of this taxonomy is the application field. The proposal defines **mobility**, **mapping**, and **interaction** as three umbrella terms under which use cases can be defined. This distinction indicates the industry, market, or milieu that the use case serves, and implicates certain minimum requirements and benchmarks in terms of performance, flexibility, and – most importantly – safety. Lastly, identifying the **technological enabler** serves as a criterion for distinguishing use cases and connecting them to trends and developments in the wider ecosystem. Emerging technologies and products are associated with industry players, sources of funding, and legislative restrictions. It is therefore highly useful to organize the use cases according to their technological foundation or cornerstone.

Now that the dimensions of our taxonomic matrix have been defined, we can begin to organize the use cases that are of special interest to our project partners. The following paragraphs present the major clusters of application scenarios that make up this consortium's catalogue.

Figure 4.1: Taxonomy of INSTINCT's use cases.

Depicted in Figure 4.1 is a projection of the use case landscape. The x-axis denotes the connectivity class, while the application fields are listed along y-axis. To fit the two-dimensional projection, key technologies are superimposed onto the 2D-plane in color where applicable. The larger circles represent thematic clusters or “super-use cases”, which broadly describe a common goal or problem of the individual cases they encompass.

1. Beginning in the top-left, a cluster dubbed **topographic mapping** is located. This cluster aims to extract information about the physical channel and its surrounding environment from communication between existing nodes in the network covering the area,

composing from it a form of topographic map. This is useful, even required, when high-directivity backhaul links sensitive to blockage and pointing error intersect with a dynamic environment, such as urban space. When a line-of-sight (LOS) link is temporarily unavailable, constructing a virtual LOS prevents link loss and therefore interruption of the vital service of high-capacity data transmission. Alternatively, assessing the topography and making informed predictions as to how it will evolve on a micro-time scale, communication load can be re-distributed to nodes with less directivity, which are not as prone to link loss at the cost of net throughput. These use cases improve the robustness of backhaul services and ensure minimal service interruption. With ultra-high fidelity, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-based RADAR, the physical mapping can be taken to the extreme in the form of detecting faults in infrastructure on a tiny scale. This could involve a swarm of UAVs inspecting a railway line for foliage creeping in or even railway tracks displaying deformities or cracks. Deployed either as regularly patrolling inspection fleets or scouting squadrons ahead of sensitive or heavy cargo transports, this use case aims to prevent accidents and maintain smooth operations in essential transit networks.

2. Closely related to these mapping schemes is the theme of utilizing stochastic geometry, also aided by sensing data, to improve the coverage in **highly dynamic urban environments**. This can involve merely extending the reach of base stations by creating paths to otherwise blocked or sparsely irradiated areas, but also incorporating non-terrestrial nodes, e.g., the previously mentioned UAVs, but also low earth orbiting (LEO) satellites, especially in dominantly vertically structured places like downtown areas with tall buildings obscuring or otherwise disrupting connectivity. Designing the coverage network according to stochastic principles and models enables it to adapt to the constantly changing environment.
3. Beyond the familiar and tightly controlled urban spaces, the multi-functional character of JCAS networks is emphasized when considering scenarios in which an **impromptu infrastructure deployment** is required. Establishing a robust communication network with large throughput generally takes large amounts of planning and optimization. The bottom-left cluster focuses on cases where connectivity is required in areas not previously covered, or when established infrastructure fails. Here, the setup of a new system is greatly aided by sensing-able networks. This can be the case in areas struck by natural disasters, where both communication and location services are direly needed for locating trapped or incapacitated victims and the limited resources must be utilized to maximum efficacy. With emergency personnel having to constantly adapt to potentially hazardous and dynamic conditions, as well as lives at stake, highly efficient and synergistic use of communication and sensing has top priority. This priority also holds true in a defensive scenario, e.g., when providing security in a sensitive location. Similarly to how noise is purposely applied to the shielding of a tap-proof communication cable, electromagnetically shadowed zones – tailored to the environment to minimize interference with outside systems – can be created by creating

a shield of disruptive signals around a zone of particular importance. This is to eavesdropping attempts what a Faraday cage is to electromagnetic fields – blocking them out and providing privacy.

4. Shifting back to more familiar spheres of application, an area especially of interest to industry and manufacturing is the one dubbed **smart kinetics**, located in the bottom right of the map of proposed use cases. Autonomous driving is adopted more and more widely in places from warehouses to public roads. But INSTINCT aims to go beyond the concept of vehicles somewhat sensorially aware of their surroundings – to drastically improve security and enable functionalities not yet possible, a critical majority of users in kinetic environments must be able to share their sensory information with the other participants, allowing decisions about individual vehicles' movement to be negotiated on the network level. An example of this form of collaboration is that of a spontaneous distributed bistatic radar, where two vehicles with radar capabilities that are not exactly co-located, but still in close proximity to one another, collaborate situationally to form a bistatic radar with enhanced radar cross section (RCS) versus the typical monostatic radar function of a single vehicle.

In an environment controlled by one entity, such as a manufacturing plant or warehouse, unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) can autonomously schedule their respective paths, avoiding collisions, minimizing idle time and requiring little to no external supervision. Taking the concept even further, entire production lines can be reconfigured on the fly by re-arranging manufacturing subsystems, conveyor belts, and temporary storage facilities. This would provide an invaluable advantage in the competitive market of industrial manufacturing, which would enable adopters to adapt to changing market conditions or trends in supply and demand with unparalleled speed.

5. When communication terminals don't provide sufficient sensory data and installing more of them is too cost-intensive, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS), sometimes also called reflective intelligent surfaces, are a promising alternative. While RIS units haven't been explicitly mentioned as a technology of interest previously, they can be applied in almost every concept discussed this far as an extension or supplement. In this group of use cases, however, **RIS units and their potential use as a sensor** are the primary objective. In particular, measuring the power of incident radiation as a function of the angle of arrival is a desirable function that can prove advantageous in many applications. The meta surfaces can also play a part in RADAR schemes, working autonomously or in conjunction with JCAS nodes to improve location accuracy, circumvent line-of-sight limitations, or elevating the location space to three dimensions. Finally, with the wealth of data that can be collected with ubiquitously deployed RIS units, extracting, organizing, and managing the large amount of information becomes a challenge in itself. Applying machine learning (ML) techniques is a highly promising approach to maximizing the efficacy of this new element of public infrastructure.

6. Finally, a research area that must not be overlooked is the **integration of novel JCAS systems into the existing 5G and future 6G infrastructure**. On a network level, this involves developing strategies for cooperation between adjacent network nodes to form multi-anchor JCAS networks, e.g., multiple UAVs jointly inspecting infrastructure with their RADAR functionality while simultaneously communicating their positions and trajectories. These enable cooperation and propagation of sensing information beyond specific tasks and on a more macro level, with fragmented sensing information being stored and synthesized when a complete set is available. To ensure seamless integration into the ecosystem, the viability of the pre-defined reference waveforms for use in a JCAS context must be evaluated.

When comparing this taxonomy of use cases to the catalogues proposed in the various standardization consortiums, it becomes apparent that especially the role of RIS units, either as an extension of conventional functions or the gateway to completely new ones, is prevalent. They can be classified as the dominant technological enabler for the majority of proposed use cases, especially when deployed in large numbers and in scenarios that rely on a collaboration of network nodes. The trend of dynamically allocating communication resources depending on current demand and the concomitant shift to more focused and situationally adapted instead of homogenous coverage is a way to cope with the exponentially increasing demand of consumers. RIS units are a prime example of this when used as beamformers, with their quick adaptability being the key to maintaining flexibility in the network. Distributing sensing duties and synthesizing or compositing information from fragmented or partial data sets is another foundation for this project. This involves employing schemes on the network layer and using techniques tried and proven in other contexts, such as Machine Learning, to improve the reliability and resolution of sensing information. Finally, bridging the air gap to incorporate non-terrestrial network (NTN) nodes is a key aspect for problems that require a high degree of flexibility and adaptability to cope with dynamically changing conditions. From micro to macro scale, this technology vastly improves the capability of our proposed JCAS solutions.

To summarize, the research topics of interest to the project partners align with those found elsewhere, with a trend towards “backbone” technologies, i.e., services that end users don’t typically interact with. Next, we provide detailed description of the main use cases and the initial requirements that are taken into account for the INSTINCT project, representing a starting point for the work that will be carried out in the different work packages. The use cases, which are described in detail in the rest of this section, are organized in the following three categories, according to the three pillars of INSTINCT:

- sensing-aided connectivity
- sensing-able connectivity
- multifunctional JCAS intelligence

4.2 Sensing-aided connectivity

4.2.1 Topographic mapping

JCAS-based, RIS-aided topographic channel mapping in high-capacity point-to-point communication links

In today's massively interconnected network of communication nodes, the backhaul network is generally thought of as primarily cable-bound. Optical fibers offer extremely low spatial interference and different streams of data can therefore be transported, stored, and processed in a highly dense configuration when necessary, such as in data centers and submarine cable assemblies. However, in inaccessible places or non-terrestrial applications, different means of linking up communication terminals have to be found. THz radiation is a well-suited candidate for bridging gaps in and extending the fiber-optic infrastructure due to its high available bandwidth and compatibility with photonic technologies, enabling seamless integration into existing networks. The main challenge in large-scale implementation lies in the high free-space attenuation in the THz band, which has to be overcome by use of high-gain antennas concentrating the transmitted energy in the LoS path. This, in turn, makes the THz terminals prone to link loss due to pointing errors and obstructions, which is detrimental in a backhaul context.

A commercially viable system, for which flexibility and uninterrupted operation is paramount, will therefore need to incorporate communication on multiple frequency bands in parallel. While the primary goal is the operation of the subsystem with the highest capacity, i.e., the THz link, for as much time as possible, lower frequency bands will serve as a fallback solution. To ensure smooth operation, it is advantageous to gather as much information as possible about the physical channel between communication terminals.

In this use case, INSTINCT aims to utilize sensing information obtained by JCAS transceivers aided by RISs to topographically map the channel between high-capacity communication terminals and its immediate environment. With static transceivers, the sensing data can be used to detect or even predict when an obstruction will occur and take action to switch operation mode to rely more on the lower frequency bands – see Figure 4.2. Such functionality is likely to be advantageous in dynamic environments such as urban centers.

Figure 4.2: RIS-aided topographic mapping in dynamic channel.

In a scenario with transceivers capable of movement or beam-steering, the information can be used to map a viable LOS path through the environment and position terminals accordingly, as depicted in Figure 4.3. This can be utilized when unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) are deployed as part of non-terrestrial networks (NTN) or even during communication with low earth-orbiting (LEO) satellites.

Figure 4.3: RIS-aided topographic mapping in static channel.

Depending on the specific application context, a RIS-aided mapping system is required to fulfill certain criteria, such as the resolution and update frequency of the mapping functionality. A selection of these system requirements and their associated KPIs is listed in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: KPI's for JCAS-based, RIS-aided topographic channel mapping.

Mapping resolution
Sounding/Mapping frequency
Sensing overhead
Net P2P data rate
Link length

The challenging requirements due to the sensitivity of the THz system are symbiotic with the potential for higher performance that the THz spectrum presents. This use case is therefore thought to be an ideal touchstone for the viability of JCAS in the next generation of mobile communication network infrastructure.

4.2.2 Dense urban coverage

RIS indoor enhanced connectivity

In an office building characterized by multiple corridors and rooms, the demand for enhanced 5G connectivity is significant. A RIS module can be strategically deployed on a wall in a corridor to extend the effective reach of a 5G base station. This deployment improves indoor coverage and signal strength, leading to better connectivity for mobile devices such as smartphones and laptops. By leveraging the RIS module, the signal can navigate through complex indoor layouts, mitigating typical signal degradation issues and ensuring consistent, high-quality 5G connectivity across different parts of the building. This not only enhances the user experience but also supports high-bandwidth applications and seamless communication within the office environment.

In a manufacturing facility, metal enclosures and equipment often cause significant signal obstruction and multipath propagation, which can degrade communication reliability. Here, RIS technology can be employed as spatial microwave modulators to manipulate existing microwave fields without requiring a direct line-of-sight. The RIS is optimized to focus electromagnetic waves, achieving notable signal enhancement even in obstructed environments. The setup involves using an iterative optimization algorithm to adjust the phase shifts of each unit cell, starting with a uniformly reflecting metasurface phase pattern. Each element of the metasurface is iteratively switched to maximize the received signal intensity, dynamically adapting to the complex environment. This approach significantly enhances signal reception, thereby improving communication reliability and efficiency within the manufacturing facility. Enhanced signal reliability is critical for supporting industrial automation, real-time monitoring, and control systems, which are essential for modern manufacturing operations.

Channel charting in the presence of time-varying controlled channel “modifiers” (RIS, analog beamformers)

Channel charting consists in the self-supervised dimensionality reduction applied to channel state information (CSI) observations. An (implicit) assumption in dimensionality reduction is that the observed random process is stationary; however, this assumption is violated if the observed channel is altered either by a time-varying analog beamformer implemented at the transmitter and/or the receiver, or through a RIS with time-varying reflection characteristics present in the scattering environment. In both cases however, the configuration of the channel “modifier” (beamformer steering direction, RIS configuration) can be assumed to be known.

Thus, here the objective is to perform dimensionality reduction based on the observation of tuples of instantaneous CSI, beamformer and RIS parameters.

Channel charting is expected to provide a pseudo-position for each mobile device in the network, for further use as a context for network management or higher layer applications, as a surrogate of position. It is not expected to solve per se a relevant end-to-end communication or sensing problem. Thus, the relevant channel charting KPIs are dimensionality reduction metrics characterizing the discrepancy between true position (ground truth) and pseudo-position.

Common topological metrics for dimensionality reduction are trustworthiness and continuity, which compare the neighborhoods of points between the two spaces. Samples sharing the same neighbors in both spaces will score positively in both metrics; samples being neighbors in one space but not another will affect the metric negatively.

For geometrical aspects, a meaningful geometrical metric is the Kruskal stress, which measures how well distances between pairs of samples in the latent space match distances in the reference space.

Channel charting-based resource allocation and RIS configuration

Here, we seek to use pseudo-position on a channel chart as a surrogate for geometric position. However, due to the self-supervised nature of the problem, position and pseudo-position do not share the same scale, and classical metrics such as quadratic error are not applicable. Thus, the general philosophy to benchmark these methods is to compare the end-to-end performance of an application using channel charting for sensing, to the ideal case where perfect ground truth information about the scene geometry is available, for the same task (e.g. dynamically configuring RIS). The metric is the natural performance indicator of the chosen application (which is typically a function of the throughputs, SINRs or packet error rates achieved by all users in the system).

The RIS-NTN use case

This use-case features an urban environment where outdoor users try to connect to the nodes of an aerial or more generally of a Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) in a LoS way using blockage sensitive spectrum, e.g., millimeter waves. In this context, understanding the connectivity of NTN entities to outdoor users on the ground is essential to optimize network planning and provide seamless network offloading and services.

The general objective of the use-case is to assess the gain (in terms of connectivity and rate) and the sensing/algorithmic cost when using RISs installed on the top of the buildings to enhance the sky visibility of outdoor users.

The setting is that where, by sensing its local skyline, the user will be able to choose the RIS that extends its sky visibility and hence NTN connectivity at best. RISs are assumed to be able to beamform to the moving NTN node and to the user equipment (UE) and should hence be of the adaptive and controlled type.

Figure 4.4: Left: the 3D model; the segments represent buildings seen from above - Right: the vision in a fixed direction where the heights and locations are depicted. The building blocking the view in this direction is denoted by a *. The RIS located on the top of this building is a natural candidate for NTN relaying.

More precisely, consider an outdoor user located in the urban environment, with its sky visibility blocked by some skyline process where each direction is blocked by some building characterized by its distance to the user (r) and its height (h). Sensing based on distance and angle allows the user to determine the (r , h) characteristics of all visible buildings on its skyline and to select an optimal one where optimality favors close-by and tall buildings according to some trade-off rule between the two. Tallness is favored because local maxima (in terms of height) are good in terms of sky visibility. Closeness from the user to the relay RIS is favored in terms of link quality.

The general idea of this use-case is to estimate the cost-to-benefit ratio of such a RIS-enhanced architecture.

- The operational benefits are in terms of gain of connectivity and rate. Several metrics can be introduced to quantify this gain, like, e.g., the gain in visibility angle due to RISs, the probability for the UE to be connected to a non-terrestrial node thanks to a RIS, given that it is not in the absence of RISs, or the gain in NTN offloading rate.
- The operational costs are in terms of sensing and algorithmic overhead. The user has to sense the skyline in order to find an optimal building/RIS. The sensed data (angles and distances) have to be processed. More sensing will lead to better benefits (e.g., higher rate) and there is hence an interesting tradeoff between sensing cost and communication benefits.

A natural KPI is the increase of spectral efficiency within this context, while taking the sensing overhead into account.

Table 4.2: KPI's for channel charting and the RIS-NTN use case.

Dimensionality reduction metrics characterizing the discrepancy between true position (ground truth) and pseudo-position.
Spectral efficiency

4.3 Sensing-able connectivity

4.3.1 UAV-aided connectivity

Using multiple UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) equipped with technology and high-fidelity radar for rail monitoring is a cutting-edge approach to maintaining and ensuring the safety of railway infrastructure. Below are some key use cases and details on how these technologies are utilized:

Rail Track Inspection and Maintenance

Crack and Defect Detection: UAVs use high-fidelity radar to detect cracks, breaks, and other structural defects in the rails. The radar provides high-resolution imaging that can identify even small defects that might be missed by traditional inspection methods.

Track Geometry Monitoring: UAVs can measure track geometry, including alignment, gauge, and elevation. JCAS ensures precise synchronization of data from multiple UAVs, allowing for comprehensive analysis of the track's condition.

Obstacle and Debris Detection

Real-time Obstacle Monitoring: UAVs can fly ahead of trains to detect obstacles or debris on the tracks in real-time. The high-fidelity radar can penetrate through fog, rain, and other adverse weather conditions, ensuring reliable monitoring.

Alert Systems: When obstacles are detected, the UAVs can communicate with each other and the control center to send alerts and initiate immediate responses, such as slowing down or stopping trains.

Environmental Monitoring

Vegetation Management: UAVs can monitor vegetation encroaching on the tracks. High-fidelity radar helps distinguish between different types of vegetation, enabling precise and targeted maintenance efforts.

Flood and Landslide Detection: UAVs equipped with radar can detect early signs of flooding or landslides that might threaten the railway. This allows for preemptive measures to be taken to ensure safety.

Structural Health Monitoring

Bridge and Tunnel Inspections: UAVs can inspect bridges, tunnels, and other structures along the railway. The high-fidelity radar can assess the integrity of these structures, identifying potential weaknesses or damage.

Synchronization for Comprehensive Coverage: JCAS ensures that data from multiple UAVs is synchronized, providing a complete picture of the structural health of railway infrastructure.

Safety and Security

Intrusion Detection: UAVs can patrol the railway perimeter to detect unauthorized access or potential security threats. High-fidelity radar can detect and track intruders, even in low-visibility conditions.

Coordination of Security Responses: JCAS allows UAVs to coordinate their movements and share real-time data, enhancing the effectiveness of security operations.

Technology Utilization

JCAS

- *Synchronization:* JCAS ensures that multiple UAVs are synchronized in their data collection efforts, reducing redundancy and increasing efficiency. This technology allows UAVs to communicate with each other to share positioning, status, and sensor data.
- *Cooperative Sensing:* UAVs can work together to form a cohesive sensing network. For instance, one UAV might focus on a specific area of the track, while another UAV covers an adjacent area, ensuring complete coverage.

High-Fidelity Radar

- *High Resolution:* The radar provides high-resolution imaging, essential for detecting fine details such as small cracks or slight misalignments in the track.
- *Adverse Conditions Operation:* High-fidelity radar is effective in all weather conditions, ensuring consistent monitoring capabilities.
- *Penetration Capabilities:* The radar can penetrate through obstacles like vegetation and minor obstructions, providing clear images of the rail tracks and surrounding infrastructure.

Table 4.3: KPI's for rail track inspection and maintenance with JCAS-equipped UAVs.

Inspection Coverage Rate
Inspection Speed
Defect Detection Rate
False Positive/Negative Rates
Resolution Quality
Cost per Kilometer of Inspection
Resource Utilization Rate
Energy Consumption

Base stations for control and surveillance of UAVs

Base stations are the nerve centers of UAV operations, providing the necessary infrastructure for control, communication, data processing, and mission management. As technology advances, these systems will become even more sophisticated, enhancing the capabilities and efficiency of UAVs across various sectors.

Consolidating UAV operations into existing base stations significantly reduces the need for multiple control units, streamlining the overall management process. This consolidation enables the coordinated control of multiple UAVs from various locations, enhancing operational efficiency and flexibility. Moreover, the system is easily scalable, allowing for the accommodation of additional base stations as the needs and scope of missions expand.

Table 4.4: KPI's for base stations for control and surveillance of UAVs.

Control Signal Range
Control Signal Reliability
Data Transmission Speed
Command Response Time
Signal Interference Rate
Data Accuracy
Latency Rate
Operational Cost
Energy Consumption

UAV-supported 5G for communication and localization in outdoor SAR scenarios

INSTINCT addresses a complex challenge of accurately localizing individuals that have gone missing during emergencies. In many instances, these individuals are unable to communicate their location due to being in remote or difficult-to-reach areas, or they might be incapacitated and unable to use their mobile devices to call for help. Each year, the inability to quickly locate these individuals results in numerous preventable fatalities, underscoring the critical need for more effective search-and-rescue tools.

Presently, the market offers various solutions for search-and-rescue operations, primarily using traditional UAVs equipped with visual detection technologies like thermal and infrared cameras or computer vision. More recently, UAVs are being adapted to serve as mobile base stations (BSs), providing network connectivity in areas where infrastructure is down or does not exist. This adaptation is crucial for enabling disaster-struck victims with mobile phones to connect and be located via their devices. The usage of a flying mobile BS not only restores communication coverage but also allows for the triangulation of cellular signals to pinpoint device locations, thereby suggesting the presence of individuals.

Current UAV-based cellular localization technologies predominantly provide two-dimensional positioning, which can be limiting. There is a pressing need for three-dimensional solutions to address scenarios where individuals may be trapped under snow, water, or debris due to

avalanches, floods, or earthquakes. Building on prior research in 4G Long Term Evolution (LTE) and earlier technologies, as indicated in Figure 4.5, we are exploring how 5G New Radio (5G-NR) enhances localization capabilities beyond those of previous generations. 5G technology, known for its high base station density and excellent temporal resolution, is revolutionizing both everyday navigation and emergency services. By integrating 5G with traditional sensing technologies, we aim to develop Intelligent Sensing and Communication (ISAC) systems. These systems are particularly promising for improving the safety and efficiency of automotive and UAV navigation in complex environments.

Figure 4.5: (a) Distance between the UAV positions and the center of the emergency area in a window time of 5 minutes (blue line). 3D positioning error in meters obtained for four tracked UEs in the same time window (red line). (b) Example of a UAV 3D prediction trajectory, obtained as output of the proposed algorithm for prediction [13].

In emergency situations, the application of 5G is transformative, enabling autonomous UAVs to perform critical tasks in areas that are otherwise inaccessible. Equipped with advanced 5G localization features, these UAVs are set to revolutionize search and rescue operations. Quick localization of personal devices, which most victims likely carry, is vital in such emergencies. This innovative application of 5G significantly enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of rescue operations, potentially saving lives.

In summary, the future of positioning and navigation services is intricately linked with 5G advancements. From enhancing daily navigation to transforming emergency response strategies, the integration of 5G into localization systems holds substantial potential to revolutionize a wide range of industries and improve public services. Our continuous exploration and improvement of these technologies are extending the boundaries of what can be achieved in terms of localization accuracy and emergency response capabilities.

Table 4.5: KPI's for SAR localization framework in emergency environments.

Positioning Accuracy Metrics: such as the measurement of SAR localization errors during specific operational periods or cumulative distribution of localization errors over time to assess consistency and reliability.

Localization Latency: a measure of the time taken from initiating a localization request to obtaining a result, which is critical in emergency situations where rapid response is necessary.
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Environmental Robustness Indicators: system's adaptability to diverse environmental conditions, implying stable localization performance under various emergency conditions such as poor lighting, presence of debris, and other physical obstacles that may impact the effectiveness of rescue operations.

Localization Reliability: system's capability of consistently providing accurate estimates.

Accuracy vs. Latency Trade-off Optimization: involving trade-offs in both system design and operational protocols to ensure that rapid responses do not result in a highly decreased localization accuracy. Different policies based on the needs of each environment. i) Policy accuracy, ii) Policy latency, iii) Clustering (trade-off between accuracy and latency).

4.3.2 RIS as a sensor

RIS in the JSAC network

JSAC, a key innovation in the 6G landscape that relies on the convergence of sensing and communication, represents a groundbreaking shift towards interconnectedness and data-driven decision-making.

This comprehensive approach empowers systems not only to transmit and receive data but also to collect, process, and leverage it for diverse applications such as localization, detection, and more. The scope of JSAC spans across various domains including smart cities, industrial automation, healthcare, and environmental monitoring, offering solutions that are not just efficient but also environmentally sustainable.

In today's rapidly advancing technological landscape, the integration of RISs has emerged as a key technology enabling ad-hoc tuning of the propagation channel. Indeed, RIS technology enables precise control over the propagation of electromagnetic waves, boosting network performance while enabling novel services and applications. These properties place RISs as enablers, unlocking the full potential of JSAC applications.

However, integrating such components presents complex challenges that can jeopardize the stability of the overall system. Existing network infrastructures may require sophisticated orchestration and management frameworks to extend their functionality for data acquisition while fulfilling their traditional communication roles. In the realm of JSAC, RIS can offer several advantages, including:

- **Enhanced Network Performance:** At the core of RIS deployment lies a significant boost in network performance. By strategically placing RISs within the network infrastructure, data transmission experiences unprecedented efficiency and reliability.
- **Improved Communication Channels:** With RIS seamlessly integrated into the network fabric, communication becomes smoother, more robust, and less susceptible to interference.
- **Localization Advantages:** RIS can become an additional, controllable, anchor point for localization services. Leveraging RIS technology, networks can boost precision in tracking and

localizing connected devices, opening doors to a plethora of location-based services and applications.

- **Sensing Capabilities:** Beyond its primary function in communication, recent works slightly modifies RIS hardware enabling them to serve jointly as channel optimizers as well as passive sensors [12]. This, in turn, adds a “sixth sense” to the network at a limited hardware and management cost. This dual-purpose functionality not only optimizes resource utilization but also enables novel applications in environmental sensing and monitoring. An example of sensed information at the RIS is provided in Figure 4.6, with a RIS capable of power sensing, which is performing directional power measurements and collecting an angular power profile. This power profile can be used to detect and locate communicating devices.

Figure 4.6: RIS with power sensing capabilities collecting directional power measurements.

RIS in ISAC deployments can benefit several use cases for the 6G network including:

- **13 Mobility:** RIS can benefit Localization, tracking applications, for example autonomous vehicles can be better located in the space by leveraging RIS as additional anchor points. A crucial role worth investigation resides in the strategic RIS deployment along roadways or within urban environment, to guarantee a precise location relative to the surrounding of vehicles and improving navigation and safety. Other applications reside in traffic management optimization, thanks to the more accurate data on vehicle movements and traffic flow. With RIS's ability to enhance communication channels and localization accuracy, traffic management algorithms can dynamically adjust traffic signals, reroute vehicles, and optimize traffic flow, thereby reducing congestion and improving overall efficiency.
- **13 Environment Monitoring:** RIS-equipped ISAC networks will enable comprehensive environmental monitoring and mapping, with RIS extending the sensing area to improve the level of detail of spatial maps. This will improve the contextual information available to the network enabling proactive decision-making and resource allocation in service areas.
- **Surveillance and Security:** RIS-enhanced ISAC networks bolster surveillance and security measures by providing enhanced situational awareness and threat detection capabilities. By strategically deploying sensing capable RIS nodes in sensitive areas, such as critical infrastructure sites or border regions, authorities can improve the detection and tracking of unauthorized intrusions, suspicious activities, or security breaches. Additionally, RIS technology

enables steering sensing capabilities of ISAC in the desired areas, allowing the creation of dynamic surveillance zones, where surveillance resources are automatically allocated and optimized based on real-time threat assessments, enhancing overall security effectiveness while minimizing resource wastage. Security can also be enhanced with RIS by means of creating on demand shadowed zones in selected areas preventing eavesdrop of the signal, as shown in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Example of privacy areas created with RIS to prevent eavesdrop of the signal [14].

Table 4.6: KPI's for RIS in the ISAC network.

JCAS service coverage enhancement.
Latency and throughput of transmissions
Bit error rate
Spectral efficiency
Localization accuracy
Detection accuracy
Sensing overhead
Relevance of input data for sensing/localization tasks, e.g., through Fisher Information analysis
Computational complexity of proposed algorithms

From RIS-as-a-sensor to mapping the environment

The vision of smart radio environments is expected to transfer them into distributed intelligent platforms that encompass communication, sensing, localization, positioning and computing capabilities. Beyond simply enhancing connectivity, RISs are expected to play an important role in environmental sensing by equipping them with energy-harvesting sensors. The ability to implement large-scale RISs will offer high precision localization and positioning services in both indoor and outdoor settings. In this sense, any radio localization and mapping system comprises three essential parts: measurements, reference systems, and estimation algorithms. The measurements which are generally collected from the radio signal between the transmitter and the receiver can be obtained from the channel estimation routine used for communication based on location-dependent metrics such as received signal strength (RSS), time of arrival (ToA), phase of arrival (PoA), angle of arrival (AoA) and angle of departure (AoD), and Doppler measurements.

The reference system is composed of anchors, the devices, RIS, etc., which possess predetermined positions and are geometrically associated with the target objects. Estimation algorithms like simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) help to establish mathematical equations which compute the position of the targets based on the measurement data and the reference positions. Beyond the target localization, RIS would also help SLAM algorithms to reconstruct the environment from one side and/or improve the coverage from the other side.

User tracking and localization

Typically, localization is performed with multiple omnidirectional antennas placed at different positions and through the processes of triangulation and trilateration. Large radiating elements, on the other hand, such as large antenna arrays (LAAs) and reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs), can flexibly operate both in the far- and near-field, offering beams from conventional beamforming to beamfocusing, characterized by small focal areas at controllable distances. Therefore, a RIS is ideal for localization purposes and offers a significantly simplified topology compared to conventional multi-antenna localization schemes. Importantly, because the RIS gradually becomes a powerful enabler of new functionalities in future wireless communications, RIS-based localization or RIS-as-a-sensor is an integral part of sensing-able wireless connectivity.

The idea of RIS-as-a-sensor is based on exploiting the RIS capabilities for wavefront engineering to operate both in the far-field and the near-field. This is possible by tailoring the radiating aperture of the RIS: with relatively small apertures, the generated beams quickly enter the far-field, enabling beam-tracking with narrow beam profile of controllable width; with relatively large apertures, the generated beams can remain entirely in the near field for the areas of interest, enabling the focusing of power at small areas with controllable focal distance.

Based on these two operations, the overall idea will be separated into two distinct phases, each related to the attributes and benefits of beamforming and beamfocusing, as shown schematically in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: Hierarchical RIS-assisted localization. Top row: Schematic illustration of the localization scheme, with the shaded regions marking the areas where the user location is successfully identified at each hierarchical level. Bottom row: simulated beams for each case.

Starting with an unknown user position, the whole procedure is divided into two phases. First, in phase 1, beam-tracking is performed with beamforming through the RIS, in order to estimate the direction of the user with respect to the RIS. Phase 1 determines the angular position of the user in a hierarchical manner, at each step separating the angular domain in a binary-tree fashion, as illustrated in Figure 4.8 (a). Subsequently, in phase 2, ranging is performed with beamfocusing through the RIS, in order to estimate the distance of the user from the RIS, along the direction identified in phase 1. Phase 2 determines the user distance from the RIS, at each step separating the radial distance in a binary-tree fashion, as illustrated in Figure 4.8 (b). After phase 2 has finished, information about both the direction and the distance is obtained, providing the location of the user within the resolution offered by each phase.

The angular resolution is determined by the minimum 3dB angular beam-width and beam-separation in phase 1 and the radial resolution is determined by the minimum size of the focal areas formed in phase 2 at each hierarchical level. For both phases, a higher hierarchical level results in finer resolution. For phase 1 the maximum number of hierarchical levels depends on the maximum desired angular resolution. For phase 2 the maximum number of hierarchical levels depends on the maximum desired radial resolution, as well as on the maximum distance that is to be scanned. For example, if the maximum distance becomes double, one more level is added with half the resolution of the previous level, and so on.

Table 4.7: KPIs for user tracking and localization.

Localization accuracy (angular, range domains)
Tracking accuracy (actual vs tracked trajectory)
Tracking overhead

4.3.3 Smart kinetics

Collision avoidance and situational awareness in vehicles

Collision avoidance and situational awareness are critical components of modern vehicle safety systems. With the advent of advanced technologies, vehicles are now equipped with sophisticated sensors and algorithms that allow them to detect and react to potential hazards in real-time. These systems, often encompassing radar, lidar, cameras, and ultrasonic sensors, work in unison to create a comprehensive understanding of the vehicle's surroundings. By continuously monitoring the environment, they can identify obstacles, pedestrians, and other vehicles, providing timely warnings to the driver or even taking autonomous actions to prevent collisions. This technological synergy not only enhances the safety of the vehicle occupants but also contributes to the overall safety of road users.

The JCAS system represents a significant advancement in this domain. JCAS integrates communication capabilities with traditional sensing technologies to create a holistic safety network. By enabling vehicles to share data about their position, speed, and trajectory, JCAS extends situational awareness beyond the individual vehicle's sensor range. This cooperative approach allows vehicles to anticipate and respond to potential dangers with greater precision and reliability. For example, a vehicle equipped with JCAS can receive alerts about sudden

braking or lane changes from other vehicles ahead, or about pedestrians crossing the road at intersections equipped with smart sensors. As a result, JCAS significantly enhances the efficacy of collision avoidance systems, leading to safer and more efficient transportation networks.

Table 4.8: KPI's for collision avoidance and situational awareness in vehicles.

Effective Coverage Area
Obstacle Detection Accuracy
False Positive/Negative Rates
Data Processing Speed
Environmental Adaptability
Collision Rate Reduction
System Installation Cost
Resource Utilization Rate

Localization and data transmission for smart transportation in industrial manufacturing plants

Industry 4.0 (I4.0) represents the next phase in the evolution of industrial manufacturing. Although the fourth industrial revolution has been recognized for some time, the transformation process is still underway, and much work remains. Furthermore, the current progress toward achieving the smart factory concept is still relatively modest.

There are many theories and initiatives related to Industry 4.0 (I4.0) that have yet to be implemented or tested in real-world scenarios. Solitary products and solutions dominate over widespread roll-outs of I4.0 concepts. Even the comprehensive I4.0 strategies presented by different companies often lack specificity for clear use cases. These developments tend to be technology-driven rather than customer-driven. While newly built factories may implement many I4.0 concepts from the start, the manufacturing processes largely remain fixed.

Conversely, customer requirements are evolving more frequently, challenging the fixed production concept. The trend is shifting from large batch production to small and individual batch production. New standards are emerging, such as lot size 1 production under large-scale conditions, highly variable factories, reduced setup times, significant reduction of investments, and fast integration of the latest manufacturing technologies.

To address these challenges, we propose several steps. The first step is transitioning from fixed production lines to a flexible manufacturing process. This transition involves introducing cyber-physical systems, digital twins, artificial intelligence, and extensive connectivity, including mobile technologies on the shop floor (see Figure 4.9). These techniques enable greater variability and flexibility in production.

The subsequent step aims to create a highly flexible factory offering complete variability. Although the physical structure—walls, floor, ceiling—remains fixed, everything else will be mobile. Assembly lines will be modular, with machines capable of moving and reorganizing into

new configurations for different purposes. They will communicate wirelessly with each other and other process functions via mobile networks and will be powered through an inductive charging system embedded in the floor. The factory of the future will be highly adaptable, flexible, and fully connected representing a very unique set of requirements on the next generation of mobile communication.

Figure 4.9: Factory of the future vision of the company Robert Bosch GmbH [Source: Bosch].

One particular application in the context of future industrial manufacturing will be addressed in this project: Improved localization and data transmission for smart transportation vehicles in future industrial manufacturing plants. This use case describes a typical driverless transport system (DTS) scenario in production environments. In this document, we focus only on two important functions of DTS often referred to as automated guided vehicles (AGV): (i) navigation that requires reliable and accurate localization and (ii) data transmission between an AGV and the corresponding application server.

In the Factory of the Future, AGVs play a crucial role in tasks such as driverless and autonomous transport of materials and goods to and from production lines. They can also carry robotic equipment, like a robot or gripper arm, to flexibly support the assembly process. An AGV fleet ensures intra-logistic transportation within the factory. Additionally, an AGV can be integrated into the assembly process by using a gripper arm with sensors to pick and place parts. Wireless high-quality video cameras can be easily mounted on mobile platforms like AGVs. The footage from these cameras can be transmitted to an image analysis system located at the "factory edge,"

enabling advanced production monitoring. This system can offer numerous new features such as accurate object detection and tracking around AGVs, anomaly detection on the shop floor, improved safety, process tracking, and logging. Our goal is to analyze the data rate and localization accuracy requirements in relation to the current state of driverless transportation systems. The requirements for this use case can be summarized as shown in the table below.

Table 4.9: KPIs for localization and data transmission for smart transportation in industrial manufacturing plants.

User requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optical and haptic feedback of the AGV state during and after its initialization as well as during and after its operation • Low delay of service initialization • Machine must run safely and correspond to functional safety requirements from IEC 61508, ISO/IEC 17025 and ISO/IEC 17020 • System operates in “zero-touch” mode after teach-in: AGV switched on and is triggered to “go” by fleet management agent based on Enterprise Resource Planning System
Functional architectural requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All operational technology components belong to a safety and security critical zone of the production and have no direct connection to the outside world incl. Internet. • To enable high flexibility of the production process, video processing functions must run on secure IT components with Internet connection. • The communication between the compute node that runs the video processing function and AGVs is controlled by a firewall.
Technical KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency for data transmission from AGV towards edge compute node • Reliability of the network service/ Packet error rate • Data rates for multiple AGV • Coverage in indoor environments within the factory facility • Mobility support • Recovery time of fail-over service • Service availability • Slice configuration/reconfiguration time • Localization accuracy during navigation/traversing • Localization accuracy during docking in supply area for on- or offload • Localization accuracy during AGV operation as part of assembly process
Relevant standards	<p>Communication networks: Standards from 3GPP, IEEE</p> <p>Functional safety: IEC 61508, ISO/IEC 17025 and ISO/IEC 17020</p> <p>EU machinery directive 2006/42/EC</p>

In Figure 4.10, we present a detailed example of an industrial manufacturing scenario from a real Bosch production plant in Stuttgart. The figure illustrates the signal strength of a mobile communication signal along the colored path of an AGV. The signal strength is highly unstable,

with numerous segments showing very poor coverage. To enhance both coverage for improved data transmission and the accuracy of AGV localization along the corridors, advanced techniques such as JCAS and RISs need to be implemented.

Figure 4.10: Operational factory environment of the company Robert Bosch GmbH in Stuttgart with deployment of a mobile communication network [Source: Bosch].

4.4 Multifunctional JCAS intelligence

4.4.1 Integration of sensing in wireless networks

Multicarrier JSAC systems, MIMO JSAC systems (co-located/distributed MIMO radar, single-/multi-user MIMO comms)

A key component of design, optimization, adaptation and learning in JSAC is to build and maintain awareness on the dynamic radio environment, joint objective functions, rewards and regret models for optimization and learning. In INSTINCT we will develop theory and methods for designing, optimizing and adapting waveforms jointly to achieve the desired performance levels in different sensing and communications tasks, and shared use of HW and spectrum resources. We will develop methods and representations for learning radio environment awareness that is used for optimizing waveforms and resource and interference management in joint sensing and communications. The awareness may consider RIS and wavefront engineering. The methods stem from structured and online optimization, model-based and model-free reinforcement learning. We will address the problem of interference management by developing spatial methods including beamformers, precoders and decoders for joint sensing and communications. In distributed and networked sensing scenarios, there is a convergence towards technologies used in distributed, fully adaptive MIMO radars.

INSTINCT will develop dual-functional waveforms with desirable properties for JCAS such that required performance levels may be achieved both in sensing and communications tasks. In addition to task specific properties, typical sensing waveforms have a close to ideal Ambiguity Function (AF), and low Peak to Average Ratio. There is a myriad of different sensing tasks with different performance criteria, starting from detecting and resolving targets and objects, estimating target parameters, tracking them, recognizing/classifying targets and characterizing micro-Doppler signatures caused by gestures, gait or moving parts. INSTINCT will derive a variety of objective functions stemming from information theory and statistical learning and inference for different JCAS tasks with operational constraints such as total power, per antenna power and maximum bandwidth as well as waveform similarity constraints. Different sensing-based services will use different objective functions and hence different waveforms. For dense spectrum use scenarios, we will design waveforms and methods to adapt them so that interferences caused to cooperative users are strictly controlled. In the proposed work orthogonal designs in frequency, code and spatial domain are a natural starting point for JCAS waveform optimization, adaptation and learning. Adaptation and learning of waveforms require awareness about the state of the spectrum, interference and target scenario. Such awareness is built by exchanging information among cooperative users. RIS systems and the possibility to engineer the propagation environment add an additional degree of freedom to waveform optimization and adaptation. We will study the use of RIS in active monostatic radar sensing.

Table 4.10: KPI's for multicarrier JSAC/MIMO JSAC.

Probability of detection / false alarm
Mean Square Error (tracking), Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB)
Mutual information, KL-divergence, Jeffrey's distance
Identifiability, i.e., # of uniquely identifiable targets (Kruskal rank)
Resolution (space/time/frequency/doppler)
Minmax (worst-case) error
Symbol/bit error rate, minimum codeword distance
Data rate, sum rate, quality of service

Sensing in cellular networks

Mobile networks are considered as enablers for a variety of applications. Although the requirements for the future cellular network development are extracted from some identified future use cases, the applications to be built on the network or utilizing network services are not fully known during the development and standardization work. INSTINCT explores JSAC in cellular networks, the emphasis being in urban and indoor environments. The sensing is assumed to be performed in bi-static or multi-anchor settings and RISs can be used to aid the sensing, communications, or both as illustrated in Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11: Cellular JSAC-RIS system.

The goal is to gain understanding of the performance limitations and trade-offs set by the resource sharing required in JSAC networks and develop efficient techniques to implement such systems. More specifically, INSTINCT considers object detection, localization, and identification (or classification) while simultaneously transmitting data or reference signals for communications. Furthermore, signal processing algorithms and performance evaluations via component and system optimization will be performed. More specifically, wideband transceiver optimization for JSAC systems will be performed and new signal designs for JSAC systems will be developed.

INSTINCT will develop the channel models for JSAC systems operating in different environments. As a use case, the environment can be scanned and mapped on low data traffic times allowing the inclusion of the clutter to channel models. As a part of the environment mapping case, the action scheduling over long time periods, such as a day, could be considered.

The considered KPIs for communications include the commonly used bit error rate (BER), symbol error rate (SER), throughput, spectral and energy efficiencies, and sum rate. Sensing KPIs include the probability of detection, the probability of false alarm, and accuracy and resolution of the parameters of interest such as range, direction, and velocity. As mentioned above, the application for the sensing has not been defined, but the results can be compared with, e.g., the numerical values of KPIs defined by 3GPP in TR22.837 in which an extensive list of use cases for ISAC has been identified. Industry Specification Group - Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISG ISAC) of European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) is also defining use cases for JSAC systems. The results of the INSTINCT project can be assessed in comparison with the ISG JSAC definitions and results.

Table 4.11: KPI's for sensing in cellular networks.

Throughput
Bit/symbol error rate
Spectral and energy efficiency
Probability of detection
Probability of false alarms
Accuracy and resolution of the parameters of interest (e.g., range, direction, distance)

Holographic Surfaces for Communication and Sensing

The JSAC framework can revolutionize the design of the physical layer of 6G networks, enabling truly sustainable 6G networks. In fact, the radio communication division of the international telecommunication union (ITU-R) has recently drafted new recommendations for the international mobile telecommunication 2030 (IMT2030) framework, the 6G telecommunication standard. In the past decade, several advanced wireless technologies, including small cells, millimeter-wave communications, and massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems, have been proposed to enhance the network capacity and to enable ubiquitous wireless connectivity. The practical implementation and deployment of these technologies is, however, often limited by the associated prohibitive energy consumption and expensive hardware equipment. As a result, it has become apparent that 6G communication networks need to undergo a fundamental shift of design paradigm, which requires to include aspects of (energy) sustainability, besides those of network capacity and connectivity, at the design stage. This change of design paradigm requires radically new physical layer technologies.

In this context, we are assisting to the upsurge in brand-new technologies for the physical layer, which rely on encoding, processing, and decoding information in the wave domain, i.e., at the electromagnetic level, as opposed to conventional physical layer technologies that rely on digital information processing. The advantages of wave domain information processing include improved computational efficiency, simplified hardware architectures, and reduced energy consumption. This emerging trend has been facilitated by recent results in the field of configurable antennas and, especially, metasurfaces, which are engineered materials capable of processing the electromagnetic waves in the wave domain without the need of analog-to-digital and digital-to-analog conversions. A physical layer technology to this end is the so-called stacked intelligent metasurface (SIM), which is a multi-layer metasurface-based devices, which resemble deep neural networks, where the data encoding and encoding is realized through signal processing operations in the wave domain. A SIM is a new device that for the first time integrates communication, sensing, and computing in a unique physical layer platform at very low complexity, high speed and efficiency. It is considered the enabling physical layer technology to realize the ISAC paradigm at the physical layer.

Typical scenarios, where SIM can be employed, include its use at the transmitter to reduce the power and the implementation complexity (see Figure 4.12) and through the networks to enhance the communication performance and enable distributed sensing, as illustrated in Figure 4.13.

Figure 4.12: SIM at the transmitter.

Figure 4.13: SIM as a network.

Table 4.12: KPI's for holographic surfaces for communication and sensing.

Signal-to-noise ratio
Signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio
Coverage probability
Rate
Spectral efficiency
Energy efficiency
Mean square error
Cramer Rao bound
Estimation accuracy
Degrees of freedom
Beamforming gain
Diversity multiplexing tradeoff
Pareto frontier

Deep Learning for Realistic Coverage Map Predictions

In wireless networks, signal attenuation occurs when the antenna signal loses strength as it travels from a transmitter to a receiver. This loss in strength can be influenced by factors such as distance, environmental conditions, including urban or rural settings, vegetation, and building materials, among others. Additionally, the height and placement of antennas and their radiation patterns can significantly impact the received signal's strength.

Radio coverage maps visually represent the Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) distribution across geographical areas, showing the strength of a network's signal. These maps are essential for network management and planning, providing insights into how mobile coverage changes across different geographical areas. This information helps network operators to optimize services, plan network expansions, and address signal-related issues. Traditionally, coverage maps are obtained through computationally intensive simulations, often requiring expensive licenses. Despite their sophistication, these models cannot fully capture the complexities of real-world environments, such as the diverse building materials and the wide range of user equipment.

Figure 4.14: General overview of our proposed method with its potential inputs and outputs.

INSTINCT aims to leverage Machine Learning (ML) techniques and crowd-sourced RSRP measurements to create more realistic coverage maps that better reflect real-world complexities. Our approach involves enhancing simulated coverage maps to bridge the gap between simulations and actual real-world conditions. We will use RSRP measurements from user equipment as our ground-truth data, representing the signal strength users experience. Our ML model will take the simulated RSRP map, along with area-related information (e.g., suburbs, parks) and other data such as building heights or network topology, to accurately predict the real-world RSRP map. This comprehensive approach aims to produce coverage maps that provide more accurate and reliable insights for network management and planning. Figure 4.14 illustrates the architecture of our proposed model, showcasing its potential inputs and outputs.

We plan to leverage various data sources to enhance the prediction capabilities of our ML model. OpenStreetMap (<https://www.openstreetmap.org/>) will provide accurate data on a wide range of features, including roads, buildings, land use, and natural elements. To extract geographic features, we will use Google Earth Engine (<https://earthengine.google.com/>), which offers a vast repository of satellite imagery and geospatial datasets. Our empirical RSRP measurements dataset will come from OpenSignal (<https://www.opensignal.com/>), a valuable source of crowd-sourced data collected from millions of mobile devices worldwide. This dataset includes detailed measurements of signal strength, network speed, and connectivity quality across diverse real-world environments. Network topology information, such as antenna locations and configurations, will be provided by the network planning team.

Initially, we will use the theoretical coverage maps developed by a network planning team from a top-tier UK MNO as input to our model. However, as a novel alternative, we plan to investigate the use of Sionna, a TensorFlow-based, differentiable, open-source library for simulating the physical layer of wireless and optical communication systems. Sionna enables rapid prototyping of complex communication system architectures using Keras layers, which can be interconnected as needed. It supports gradients backpropagation through entire systems, facilitating system optimization and machine learning, particularly the integration of neural networks. We intend to

leverage Sionna's robust simulation features to generate theoretical coverage maps with accurate and detailed representations of signal strength.

Table 4.13: KPI's for deep learning for realistic coverage map predictions.

Coverage prediction accuracy (relative to empirical measurements of coverage in an operational RAN deployment)
Mean Absolute Error
Mean Squared Error
Root Mean Squared Error
Reference Signal Received Power

4.5 Summary of critical KPI's

In Table 4.14, we summarize the KPI's that are most critical to the INSTINCT use cases, and were previously presented in detail for each individual use case. Because both sensing and communications are integral part of all three pillars of INSTINCT, the categorization in Table 4.14 highlights the KPI's most relevant to each pillar.

Table 4.14: Summary of most critical KPI's for the three pillars of INSTINCT.

Sensing-aided connectivity	Sensing-able connectivity	Multifunctional JCAS
Throughput	Accuracy (tracking, localization)	SNR/SINR
Latency	Resolution (space/time/frequency)	Mean square/absolute error
Bit/symbol error rate	Mobility support	Cramer Rao bound
Overhead	Coverage	Spectral and energy efficiency
Data rate, sum rate, quality of service	Spectral and energy efficiency	Coverage prediction accuracy
Probability of detection / false alarm	Overhead	Reference Signal Received Power
Spectral and energy efficiency	Latency	RIS coverage enhancement
Resolution (space/time/frequency)	Data transmission/processing speed	Reconfiguration latency
	Bit/symbol error rate	Diversity multiplexing tradeoff

5 Initial considerations on system architecture and performance evaluation methodology

In this section, we introduce the overall methodology for delivering the envisioned INSTINCT contributions, together with the envisioned performance evaluation strategies identified to evaluate the JCAS wireless network performance across relevant scenarios and with initial considerations on the system architecture component and network deployment strategies that are considered in INSTINCT.

5.1 Overall methodology

The INSTINCT consortium has defined a three-phase methodology plan to drive the development and the performance evaluation plan.

- Phase 1 is focusing on the Theoretical Framework Development, and has the broad objective of defining application scenarios, use cases, requirements, system concepts models and suitable KPIs/KVIs. This is done by means of the identification of relevant 6G applications and group them into 13 main usage scenarios 13 mobility, 13 monitoring, and 13 Internet of Senses, while extracting system-level requirements and KPIs and KVIs and translate them into hardware and system specifications, together with developing system and network architectures including INSTINCT enablers such as RIS, holographic MIMO, radar based sensing, JCAS and AI, and establishing novel theoretical frameworks integrating communication and sensing theory.
- Phase 2 is focusing on the Ecosystem Development, focusing on designing key hardware and software elements to enhance system and network energy and spectral efficiency. This includes developing advanced JCAS antenna and transceiver solutions, RIS, holographic radios, and sensing modules, along with software algorithms for DSP and baseband concepts. These designs incorporate the requirements and specifications defined in Phase I. Additionally, the phase develops advanced JCAS connectivity solutions, resource management strategies, and model-based and data-driven approaches for ML-based network optimization.
- Phase 3 focuses on the Ecosystem Demonstration and Evaluation, with the objective to validate and test the key technologies and algorithms developed in Phases 1 and 2 via proof-of-concept. It involves delivering two hardware demonstrators: one focused on sensing intelligence and another on RIS and holographic radios as sensors, utilizing technologies from Phase II. The demonstration scenarios are derived from the use cases defined in Phase I. Additionally, a software demonstrator is implemented to showcase the benefits of co-designed sensing and communication systems, further enhanced by the AI/ML approaches developed in Phase II. Moreover, the INSTINCT consortium will develop

hardware setups as proof-of-concept to demonstrate and validate the feasibility of the techniques developed and allow KPIs and KQIs evaluation in a controlled environment. Other scenarios will be explored through a link- and system-level simulation platform, modeling outdoor environments, interference, and high-Doppler conditions.

5.2 Performance evaluation strategies

To effectively evaluate the performance of JCAS networks, a comprehensive methodology is needed. This methodology must account for the unique challenges and trade-offs inherent in integrating communication and sensing functionalities. In contrast to traditional communication network performance evaluation and the performance evaluation of technologies specifically developed for performing the sensing tasks, JCAS necessitates a dual-focus approach. By highlighting the differences between traditional communication and sensing performance evaluation, this methodology provides a comprehensive approach to assessing JCAS systems. This dual-focus evaluation is essential for developing robust and efficient JCAS applications across various domains. Here below some considerations on the aspects to be considered in evaluating JCAS performances.

5.2.1 Analytical studies

Analytical frameworks are essential for studying the performance bounds and for characterizing various wireless system concepts (RIS, cell-free MIMO, wavefront engineering) for JCAS. Explicit electromagnetic modeling, as a means for developing an electromagnetic information theory framework, is crucial for studying the RIS-as-a-sensor, beamforming / beamtracking techniques for RIS-enabled localization, and beams with advanced beamforming capabilities for holographic MIMO communications. With tailored analytical tools, several performance metrics relevant to JCAS can be assessed, such as the received power and energy efficiency, the localization accuracy and resolution, and multi-user interference.

For example, the theoretical characterization of performance can be done by representing network elements employing stochastic point processes, and different propagation conditions using stochastic geometry approaches. These theoretical frameworks can then be leveraged to extract performance metrics such as coverage or Shannon rate and sensing capacity, which are functionals of these processes. JCAS-related performance metrics can then be evaluated statistically over the considered area. Another advantage of such analytical tools is that they provide a comprehensive means for system-level analysis of large wireless networks, which are generally difficult to evaluate in testbeds, as well as a reduction of large data sets to a small number of parameters. This, in turn, allows for network optimization in the function of its parameters.

5.2.2 Network performance evaluation

In traditional communication networks, performance metrics such as throughput, latency, and reliability are primarily influenced by network load and channel conditions. For JCAS, however, it

is crucial to develop analytical models and simulations that also consider the impact of sensing requirements. A suitable channel model must capture the geometry of the channel environment, including static components like infrastructure and dynamic components like moving targets and obstacles. This dual focus ensures that both communication and sensing performance are accurately represented and combined. Resource allocation typically focuses on optimizing time, frequency, and power usage to maximize throughput and minimize latency. Conversely, in JCAS networks, resource allocation must also consider the requirements of sensing tasks. This involves developing analytical models to investigate optimal strategies for sharing resources such as time, frequency, antennas, and power between communication and sensing. The impact of sensing data exchange and fusion on network overhead and communication requirements must be thoroughly studied to ensure a balanced allocation that supports both functionalities. Finally, traditional communication networks employ techniques like orthogonal waveform design, beamforming, and scheduling to mitigate interference. In JCAS networks, these techniques must also account for sensing requirements. Simulations should capture the impact of sensing metrics (e.g., target detection accuracy) on communication performance under varying network loads. Analytical models are needed to characterize the trade-offs between communication and sensing performance based on waveform parameters and resource allocation, highlighting the unique challenges of JCAS.

5.2.3 JCAS performance evaluation

Evaluating performance of dedicated sensing infrastructures, typically involves analyzing metrics such as detection range, resolution, accuracy, and target classification capabilities. In JCAS networks, these metrics must be assessed under different network configurations and channel conditions that also support communication tasks. Accurate models that capture the geometry and dynamics of the propagation environment, including both static infrastructure and moving targets, are essential. Additionally, sensing performance can be affected by environmental factors and hardware limitations. In JCAS networks, additional communication impairments such as interference, multipath, and hardware imperfections also play a significant role. Evaluating how these aspects impact sensing performance is crucial for developing robust JCAS systems. This dual focus on both communication and sensing impairments distinguishes JCAS performance evaluation from that of traditional sensor networks.

5.2.4 Experimental testbeds and prototypes

Developing hardware testbeds and prototypes is a common practice in both communication and sensor networks to validate theoretical models and simulations. For JCAS networks, these testbeds must integrate both communication and sensing functionalities on the same hardware platform. Implementing signal processing algorithms for joint waveform design, beamforming, and data fusion on advanced hardware platforms such as software-defined radio platforms and FPGAs, capable of executing complex signal processing tasks is essential. Evaluating performance trade-offs experimentally under realistic conditions provides valuable insights that theoretical models alone cannot offer. Moreover, it is necessary to develop use case-specific evaluation frameworks that consider the combined impact of communication and sensing on application-level performance metrics. Analyzing the impact of JCAS on such metrics, along with

investigating business models and economic incentives for deploying JCAS-based services, is crucial for a holistic evaluation.

Below, we provide a preliminary description of the experimental testbeds and platforms that are currently considered by the INSTINCT consortium to practically evaluate proposed approaches:

CorteXlab software-defined radio platform

CorteXlab is a testbed initially founded in the French program EquipEx from 2009 to 2021, and now supported in the PEPR-5G (Future Investment program). CorteXlab is a part of the French node (SLICES/FR) of the European infrastructure SLICES. As such, CorteXlab will be connected to the SLICES infrastructure with a full 5G protocol stack developed by the SLICES consortium. The current configuration allows experimentation in situ, remotely programable and controllable. CorteXlab will be made available for the consortium to run and demonstrate new waveforms, signal processing, and algorithms dedicated to machine learning empowered intelligent JCAS networks. This will constitute a first and worldwide unique experimental assessment of communication and sensing protocols. The use of CorteXlab will fasten the deployment of a real proof of concept, integrating contributions from all partners.

Figure 5.1: Left: Schematic of Cortex Lab infrastructure with multiple software defined radio nodes. Right: Related synchronization mechanisms.

Hardware testbeds

As a key technology item, a 28 GHz RIS prototype developed by GW within the project will be used. To test the RIS prototype, GW lab is equipped with three B210 Software Defined Radios (SDRs) from Ettus, three computing devices equipped with Open Air Interface (OAI), a RIS, two up/down converters, two horn antennas, and three omnidirectional antennas. For the wideband JCAS experiments, FHG-HHI will upgrade the RIS testbed with its wideband testbed equipment comprising multi-antenna transmit and receive antenna arrays (8x8 elements), and wideband

DACs and ADCs with bandwidths beyond 50 GHz, e.g. allowing for direct RF synthesis with full digital control at 28 GHz.

Figure 5.2: Left: GW End-to-End 5G RIS testbed with dynamic RIS control. Right: FHG-HHI wideband testbed (direct RF synthesis) with integrated RIS.

Experimental evaluation of RIS real-world benefits

In an effort to further address the limitations in terms of radio coverage some operators experience, we plan to evaluate via testbed deployment the benefits of various RIS prototypes. Specifically, we plan to use the Victoria Network testbed (part of the 6G-SANDBOX project) to integrate RIS prototypes and evaluate their performance in real-world scenarios. The figure below provides an overview of the current architecture of the Victoria Network testbed in Malaga, Spain. As part of the University Campus deployment, we aim to evaluate the gains in terms of radio coverage that RIS prototypes can offer.

Figure 5.3: Experimental evaluation of RIS real-world benefits.

5.3 System architecture considerations

With a focus on JCAS management, the INSTINCT network architecture needs to adapt to diverse service needs, harmonizing network intelligence solutions and investigating novel deployment and management strategies. To this aim, it will integrate machine learning for resource allocation, control, and anomaly detection, and feature AI-based orchestration for closed control loops, enhancing decision-making with continuous feedback. Moreover, edge platforms optimize resource allocation and support deep learning models for control and management tasks. Some initial considerations are drawn to guide the development of the JCAS network architecture as follows.

Key Design Principles: The design principles guiding our network architecture development include scalability, ensuring the architecture can grow with increasing numbers of sensors and reflecting surfaces, and flexibility, incorporating modular components that can be adapted or replaced as new technologies and requirements emerge. Real-time adaptation will enable dynamic optimization of network performance. Resilience and robustness will be achieved through mechanisms for detecting and mitigating anomalies, ensuring continuous and reliable network operation. Finally, edge and cloud integration will balance processing tasks to optimize latency and computational load, leveraging the strengths of both environments.

Resource Allocation and Control: To advance the capabilities of JCAS networks, we aim to develop cutting-edge machine learning algorithms for resource allocation, control, and coordination, particularly in multi-sensory environments and systems with multiple RISs involved. These algorithms will enhance the management of network resources, enabling more efficient and effective operations and will reside in a centralized AI-based orchestrator and controller for JCAS networks. This orchestrator will leverage AI to coordinate various network elements, ensuring seamless and efficient operations. The network architecture will integrate network intelligence solutions across communication, sensing, and computing domains, facilitating seamless interactions between different network components.

Integration of multi-Sensory and multiple RIS components in the network: For effective resource allocation and coordination, the network will integrate machine learning models to fuse data from various sensors, producing reliable low-dimensional representations. Self-supervised representations, such as channel charting, will be used to understand and predict the scattering environment effectively. Control mechanisms will utilize a combination of DNNs and classical statistical models to manage real-world scenarios, supported by heuristics and optimization tools tailored to diverse network operation conditions. AI-based anomaly detection systems, implemented using crowd-sourced measurements and drive tests, will help identify and address irregularities. Moreover, investigating novel deployment strategies for JCAS-capable systems will help optimize the placement and operation of network elements for maximum efficiency and performance, both in terms of communication and in terms of sensing capabilities. AI-driven simulations will also guide the strategic deployment of RISs, enhancing network coverage.

AI-Based Orchestration: A centralized AI-based orchestrator will operate in closed control loops, continuously recording context and collecting quality observations to refine and improve

decision-making processes. The integration of learning and orchestration modules within a system-level simulator will manage control and data planes, supporting real-time learning without human intervention, particularly for RIS-specific orchestration.

Network Management and Edge Integration: The overall network architecture will be designed to learn, sense, reason, optimize, and adapt to diverse service requirements. This architecture will integrate network intelligence solutions seamlessly for communication and sensing. Innovative deployment strategies will be investigated and implemented for JCAS-capable systems, considering both RIS and non-RIS environments. Strategies for managing hot spots will enhance both sensing and communication capabilities. Additionally, optimal strategies for allocating edge resources to preprocess measurement data and execute deep learning models will be defined, with a focus on determining the best locations for deploying edge resources to support the management and control of smart surfaces.

6 Conclusions

In deliverable D1.1 the identified use cases and system requirements that are considered relevant for the INSTINCT project have been presented. Also, the main KPI's that the overall INSTINCT system concept has to satisfy were introduced. The use cases in INSTINCT have been classified in three general categories, namely:

- sensing-aided connectivity
- sensing-able connectivity
- multifunctional JCAS intelligence

The above taxonomy reflects the INSTINCT system concept and innovative features. For each category, details on the topology and the main features of the relevant use cases were provided. The main KPIs that were analyzed here, will be used as input to other work packages, in order to enable the detailed investigation of each scenario in the course of the project. Finally, a description of the performance evaluation methodology that will be applied in the framework of INSTINCT was presented.

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